

COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
MASTER IN MATHEMATICS AND SCIENTIFIC MODELING
MASTER'S THESIS
ACADEMIC YEAR [2024-2025]

TÍTULO:

Quantum Simulation and Variational Quantum Methods to solve the Alternated Exchange Heisenberg Model.

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Abstract

In this Master's Thesis, we conduct an in-depth study of the Alternating-Exchange Heisenberg Model (AEHM), a one-dimensional system of spins $S = \frac{1}{2}$ that exhibits a interesting phenomenology associated with dimerization, the opening of a spectral gap, and the emergence of topological edge modes. The behavior of the model is analyzed from a dual perspective: through classical numerical simulations and hybrid quantum algorithms, with the aim of evaluating its spectral structure, correlation properties, and its potential to generate spin currents analogous to the bulk photovoltaic effect.

First, a classical study is carried out using the QuSpin library, where the properties of the AEHM are explored for different chain lengths, boundary conditions, and coupling ratios. We characterize the transition between the uniform gapless regime and the strongly dimerized regime, as well as the appearance of edge states under certain conditions. Local correlations and magnetization profiles are also computed, allowing us to distinguish between trivial and nontrivial topological phases through the *bulk-boundary* correspondence.

Second, a variational scheme based on the *Variational Quantum Eigensolver* (VQE) algorithm is implemented to approximate the ground state of the AEHM using ansätze inspired by *valence-bond* states. We analyze the convergence of the method, its dependence on circuit depth, and its ability to faithfully reproduce the results obtained through exact diagonalization. This study makes it possible to assess the feasibility of hybrid algorithms for investigating strongly correlated systems in the NISQ era.

Finally, we discuss the relevance of the AEHM as a platform for exploring spin-transport phenomena, particularly the generation of optically induced spin currents analogous to the *bulk photovoltaic effect*. The results show that the combination of classical simulation and quantum algorithms provides an effective framework for investigating *many-body* systems and opens the door to future applications in quantum computing, spintronics, and topological materials.

Keywords: Quantum Computing, Spin Chains, Heisenberg Model, Variational Quantum Eigensolver, Spin Photovoltaic Effect.

Resumen

En este Trabajo de Fin de Máster se estudia en profundidad el modelo de Heisenberg con canje alterno (AEHM), un sistema unidimensional de espines $S = \frac{1}{2}$ que presenta una interesante fenomenología asociada a la dimerización, la apertura de un gap espectral y la aparición de modos de borde de naturaleza topológica. Se analiza el comportamiento del modelo desde una perspectiva doble: mediante simulaciones numéricas clásicas y a través de algoritmos cuánticos híbridos, con el fin de evaluar su estructura espectral, sus correlaciones y su posible capacidad para generar corrientes de espín análogas al efecto fotovoltaico de volumen.

En primer lugar, se lleva a cabo un estudio clásico mediante la librería QuSpin, donde se exploran las propiedades del AEHM para distintos tamaños de cadena, condiciones de contorno y relaciones de acoplo. Se caracteriza la transición entre el régimen uniforme sin gap y el régimen fuertemente dimerizado, así como la aparición de estados de borde en ciertas condiciones. Asimismo, se calculan correlaciones locales y distribuciones de magnetización, que permiten distinguir entre fases topológicas triviales y no triviales mediante la correspondencia *volumen-borde*.

En segundo lugar, se implementa un esquema variacional basado en el algoritmo *Variational Quantum Eigensolver* (VQE) para aproximar el estado fundamental del AEHM mediante ansatz inspirados en estados tipo *valence bond*. Se analiza la convergencia del método, su dependencia con la profundidad del circuito y su capacidad para reproducir con alta fidelidad los resultados obtenidos mediante diagonalización exacta. Este estudio permite valorar la viabilidad de los algoritmos híbridos en el análisis de sistemas fuertemente correlacionados en la era NISQ (Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum). [39]

Finalmente, se discute la relevancia del AEHM como plataforma para explorar fenómenos de transporte de espín, en particular la generación de corrientes inducidas ópticamente análogas al *bulk photovoltaic effect*. Los resultados muestran que la combinación de simulación clásica y algoritmos cuánticos constituye una herramienta eficaz para investigar sistemas de muchos cuerpos y abre la puerta a futuras aplicaciones en computación cuántica, espintrónica y materiales topológicos.

Palabras clave: Computación Cuántica, Cadenas de espín, Modelo de Heisenberg, Variational Quantum Eigensolver y Efecto Fotovoltaico de Espín.

Contents

1	Introduction	5
1.1	The problem of quantum modeling	6
1.2	Spin models as reference systems for the study of many-body physics . . .	7
1.3	The use of quantum computers to address the many-body problem	8
1.4	The Heisenberg model with alternating exchange	10
1.5	The bulk photovoltaic effect and its spin analog	11
1.6	Objectives of the Master's Thesis	12
2	Methods for Solving the Heisenberg Model with Alternating Exchange	13
2.1	Diagonalization and properties of the model	13
2.1.1	Heisenberg dimer	14
2.1.2	Finite Heisenberg chain	16
2.1.3	Heisenberg chain with alternating exchange	19
2.2	Variational Quantum Eigensolver	25
2.3	Dynamical evolution of the model	26
3	Results. Exploration of spin currents for the AEHM	35
4	Variational Quantum Eigensolver	43
5	Conclusions	50
	References	51
	Appendix I	55
	Appendix II	60

1 Introduction

The study of quantum many-body systems constitutes one of the most relevant challenges of contemporary physics. These systems are characterized by the presence of strongly correlated interactions among a large number of particles, which gives rise to collective phenomena that cannot be described using simple independent-particle approximations. Within this framework, spin models have historically played a fundamental role, since they make it possible to capture essential properties of magnetic materials and exotic quantum phases through conceptually simple formulations. In particular, the one-dimensional Alternated Exchange Heisenberg Model (AEHM) constitutes a case of special interest due to its phenomenological richness and the connections it establishes with the physics of topological matter [1].

The AEHM model describes one-dimensional chains of $S = 1/2$ spins in which the exchange interactions between neighboring spins alternate periodically. This feature introduces a modulation in the lattice that breaks the homogeneity of the conventional Heisenberg model and leads to the emergence of singular properties. Among them, the presence of a spectral gap in the bulk states and the existence of localized edge modes under open boundary conditions stand out. These properties are indicative of the topological character of the model, in which the so-called bulk–edge correspondence is manifested explicitly. The AEHM has thus become a reference system in the study of topological phases in low dimensions.

Beyond its theoretical relevance, the AEHM model finds applications in experimental contexts of growing interest. In particular, it has been shown to describe with remarkable fidelity the electronic and magnetic properties of artificial nanographene chains, systems that have recently been synthesized and that offer a versatile platform to explore topological physics in organic-based materials [2]. Likewise, the AEHM model has been proposed as a candidate to exhibit nontrivial transport responses, such as the generation of spin currents in the absence of relevant static magnetic fields, in a phenomenon that may be referred to as a photovoltaic spin response [1] [4]. These types of effects open the door to the design of quantum devices in which the coherent dynamics of spins is directly exploited as a technological resource.

From a methodological point of view, the study of the AEHM model provides an ideal scenario for comparing classical and quantum simulation strategies. On the one hand, the development of computational packages such as QuSpin makes it possible to implement efficient algorithms on classical computers for the construction and diagonalization of spin

Hamiltonians, facilitating the analysis of spectra, correlators, and transport properties. On the other hand, the advent of quantum computers opens new possibilities for addressing these same problems with variational techniques such as the *Variational Quantum Eigensolver* (VQE), which allow one to approximate ground states on general-purpose quantum devices [12]. A systematic comparison of both approaches is not only of great educational interest, but also contributes to delineating the current limits and future prospects of quantum computing applied to condensed matter physics.

In this Master's Thesis, the study of the Heisenberg model with alternating exchange will be addressed from a dual perspective. First, its spectral and correlation properties will be analyzed through classical simulations with QuSpin, delving into the role of boundary conditions and the possible emergence of transport responses. Second, a hybrid algorithm based on VQE will be designed and implemented to approximate the ground state of the model, comparing its results with those obtained by classical simulation and evaluating the feasibility of extending its application to real quantum hardware. In this way, the work is situated at the intersection of spin model theory, classical numerical simulation, and the development of quantum algorithms, offering a broad and up-to-date view of one of the most stimulating problems at the frontier of quantum physics and computation.

1.1 The problem of quantum modeling

The study of quantum many-body systems presents a fundamental obstacle that limits both classical simulations and implementations on quantum hardware: the dimension of the Hilbert space grows exponentially with the number of particles or degrees of freedom of the system. This phenomenon, known as the quantum “curse of dimensionality,” constitutes one of the main barriers to the exact description of realistic systems. In a system composed of N sites (or spins) of local dimension d , for example, $d = 2$ for $S = 1/2$ spins, the total state space is the tensor product of the local spaces and has dimension

$$\dim(\mathcal{H}) = d^N,$$

which implies that each new site multiplies the size of the accessible space by d [13]. This scaling translates into the fact that storing the full state vector or explicitly representing the operators becomes prohibitively expensive: even for spin chains of moderate length, the memory consumption grows faster than the resources available on classical computers. In practice, it will be seen in this work that exact diagonalization methods reach their computational limit for systems of only a few tens of spins.

Moreover, the presence of strongly correlated interactions further aggravates this complexity, since the number of determinants or configurations required to describe the quantum state increases in a non-polynomial manner with the system size [28]. This behavior affects both classical simulations and hybrid quantum algorithms. In the classical domain, for example with packages such as QuSpin, memory cost prevents access to larger spin chain sizes. In quantum computing, although in principle a quantum processor can directly manipulate amplitudes in a space of dimension d^N , the preparation, control, and measurement of strongly entangled states remain nontrivial technical challenges [31].

For these reasons, an essential part of current research in condensed matter physics and quantum simulation focuses on developing strategies that mitigate this exponential growth. Among them are renormalization techniques, tensor networks, and variational approaches, as well as hybrid (classical–quantum) algorithms such as the *Variational Quantum Eigensolver* (VQE). Under certain correlation structures or with limited entanglement, these methodologies make it possible to reduce the effective simulation cost and access larger systems [39].

In this context, the Heisenberg model with alternating exchange acquires particular interest: the modulation in the couplings introduces a spatial structure that partially simplifies the form of the ground state and allows techniques to be applied more efficiently. Thus, the study of this model is not only relevant due to its intrinsic physical interest, but also as a testbed for evaluating the effectiveness of different numerical approaches in the face of the challenge of exponential scaling, as will be seen in this Master’s Thesis.

1.2 Spin models as reference systems for the study of many-body physics

Spin models constitute a paradigmatic tool in the study of quantum many-body systems. Their discrete formulation and relative formal simplicity make it possible to capture, in a controlled manner, collective phenomena and quantum correlation effects that also appear in real materials [23]. In this sense, they are commonly used as *toy models* (simplified reference models) that allow fundamental questions about entanglement, phase transitions, or the emergence of order in low dimensions to be explored.

One of the main attractions of these models lies in the fact that, despite their apparent simplicity, they exhibit extremely rich physics and, in some cases, are accessible almost exactly either analytically or numerically. For example, the one-dimensional Ising model in a transverse field and the one-dimensional antiferromagnetic Heisenberg model possess

exact solutions that have made it possible to establish rigorous results regarding the structure of their spectra [29], the presence or absence of gaps, and the behavior of correlations [28]. These systems serve as testbeds for validating approximate methods and for understanding the mechanisms underlying more complex quantum phases.

Furthermore, the existence of exact theorems, such as the Lieb–Schultz–Mattis theorem [29] or Haldane’s conjecture for integer and half-integer spins [30], provides a solid conceptual framework for classifying quantum phases and understanding the relationship between symmetry, dimensionality, and excitation spectra. These results have had a profound impact both on condensed matter theory and on the development of low-energy effective models.

In parallel, the development of specialized numerical techniques for one-dimensional systems, in particular the *Density Matrix Renormalization Group* (DMRG) [31], has made it possible to obtain highly accurate numerical solutions for spin chains of sizes far beyond those accessible through exact diagonalization [3]. This method exploits the fact that ground states of 1D systems with local interactions exhibit limited entanglement, which enables an efficient representation using tensor networks. For this reason, one-dimensional spin models constitute an ideal testing ground for comparing and validating new methodologies, both classical and quantum, including variational algorithms implemented on quantum hardware.

In the context of the present work, the Heisenberg model with alternating exchange belongs to this family of model systems: it combines a simple structure, treatable with advanced numerical techniques, with an interesting phenomenology ranging from the opening of topological gaps to the emergence of edge modes. Its study therefore offers an opportunity to concretely explore how classical diagonalization methods and hybrid quantum–classical strategies address the challenge of entanglement in the many-body regime.

1.3 The use of quantum computers to address the many-body problem

As mentioned above, the emergence of quantum computing has opened a promising avenue for the study of many-body systems, offering the possibility of representing and manipulating quantum states natively in physical hardware. In principle, a quantum processor with a sufficient number of qubits can directly explore a Hilbert space of exponential dimension, suggesting that certain problems intractable for classical computation could

be solved more efficiently using quantum algorithms. However, the practical translation of this idea to the concrete study of spin models or strongly correlated systems poses considerable conceptual and technical challenges.

In the context of quantum simulation of Hamiltonians, two strategies have become established as reference approaches: Quantum Phase Estimation (QPE) algorithms [33] and hybrid variational methods, among them the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE) [39], which will be discussed in this project. Both aim to estimate the ground state or eigenvalues of a Hamiltonian, but they do so from very different perspectives.

The Phase Estimation algorithm is one of the major cornerstones of universal quantum computing. In an ideal scenario, it allows one to determine with high precision the eigenvalues of a unitary operator associated with the system Hamiltonian, achieving an exponential advantage compared to classical diagonalization methods. Nevertheless, its practical application requires deep circuits, high gate fidelities, and the availability of an initial state with significant overlap with the target state. These requirements make its implementation on current noisy and decoherent quantum devices, for the time being, hardly viable [36].

By contrast, the variational approach of VQE is better suited to NISQ-era quantum hardware. In this method, the quantum processor is used to prepare and measure parameterized states, while a classical optimizer adjusts those parameters to minimize the expected energy of the Hamiltonian. This hybrid structure reduces circuit depth requirements and allows reasonably accurate approximations of the ground state to be obtained with a limited number of qubits and operations. However, the accuracy of the result depends critically on the form of the chosen variational ansatz and on the efficiency of the optimization process, which may be affected by issues such as the presence of multiple local minima or even barren plateaus [20].

Thus, QPE and VQE represent two complementary extremes within the spectrum of quantum strategies for the many-body problem: the former exemplifies the theoretical potential of large-scale quantum computing, while the latter reflects its pragmatic implementation in current technology. In the framework of this work, the focus will be on the variational approach, which constitutes the most realistic route for exploring the physics of spin models on contemporary quantum hardware. Nevertheless, the conceptual contrast between both methods makes it possible to place VQE within a broader panorama, where the ultimate goal remains to understand to what extent quantum computers can offer a tangible advantage in solving many-body problems.

1.4 The Heisenberg model with alternating exchange

In this section, the model that gives rise to the entire development of this work will be presented: the Heisenberg model with alternating exchange (AEHM). This model describes a one-dimensional chain of $S = 1/2$ spins with exchange interactions that alternate periodically between two different values. Its Hamiltonian can be expressed in general form as

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^N J_i \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1}, \quad J_i = \begin{cases} J_1, & \text{if } i \text{ is odd,} \\ J_2, & \text{if } i \text{ is even,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where J_1 and J_2 are the alternating coupling constants and \mathbf{S}_i represents the spin operator at site i . The alternation of the couplings introduces a dimerized modulation in the lattice that breaks the translational invariance of the uniform Heisenberg model and gives rise to a more interesting bond structure from a physical point of view.

This dimerization has profound consequences for the spectral and topological behavior of the system. In particular, the AEHM exhibits the opening of an energy gap in the excitation spectrum of the ground state. Under open boundary conditions, this model can host localized edge modes, low-energy states confined at the ends of the chain, which disappear when periodic boundary conditions are considered. This difference between the spectral structure of open chains and rings reflects a characteristic feature of the topology of the system: the existence of a bulk–edge correspondence, analogous to that observed in fermionic models such as the Su–Schrieffer–Heeger (SSH) model [14].

In fact, the AEHM can be interpreted as the spin analog of the SSH model, in which the alternation of couplings plays a role equivalent to the breaking of inversion symmetry in a semiconductor [25, 9]. Depending on the relation between the parameters J_1 and J_2 , the system can be found in different phases: a trivial phase, in which the spins form singlets on the stronger bonds, and a topological phase, characterized by the presence of nearly degenerate edge states.

From an experimental point of view, interest in the Heisenberg model with alternating exchange has grown significantly in recent years thanks to advances in the control of quantum systems at the nanometric scale. In particular, it has been shown that this model describes with high accuracy the electronic and magnetic properties of synthetic nanographene chains assembled atom by atom on surfaces [34, 37]. In these structures, the alternation of exchange couplings emerges from the geometric modulation of the bonds between aromatic units, generating an effectively dimerized physics that reproduces the behavior of the AEHM.

Complementarily, the AEHM also constitutes a reference model from a theoretical perspective, serving as a bridge between the physics of inversion-symmetry-broken semiconductors and one-dimensional quantum magnetic systems [37]. The alternation of couplings introduces an effective breaking of spatial symmetry that gives rise to nontrivial transport behaviors, analogous to those of topological materials with charge or spin polarization. This correspondence between fermionic and spin descriptions underscores the value of the AEHM as a model system for exploring the emergence of topological phases in contexts where quantum correlations play an essential role.

1.5 The bulk photovoltaic effect and its spin analog

The main motivation of this work will be to study an effect that occurs in certain systems, known as the bulk photovoltaic effect. But what does this mean? In materials without spatial inversion symmetry, exposure to an oscillating electromagnetic field can induce a continuous electric current even in the absence of an external potential. This phenomenon, known as the bulk photovoltaic effect (BPVE), manifests itself as a nonlinear response of the system to an alternating (AC) perturbation. Qualitatively, the generated current, known as the shift current, is proportional to the square of the amplitude of the applied field, reflecting its second-order nature in response theory [4].

Unlike the conventional photovoltaic effect, in which the current arises from the separation of carriers generated by an external electric field, the BPVE is intrinsic to the material and is directly related to its electronic structure. Its occurrence requires the breaking of inversion symmetry, which allows the electronic states of the conduction band and the valence band to respond asymmetrically to optical excitation. From a topological point of view, the *shift current* is associated with geometric quantities in Bloch space, in particular with the Berry connection and Berry curvature [4] [6], which characterize the coherent response of electrons to the applied field.

The concept of shift current can be extended analogously to the case of spin degrees of freedom, giving rise to the so-called spin photovoltaic effect or *spin-shift current* [7]. In this phenomenon, the alternating excitation of the system generates a net spin current, that is, a directional flow of angular momentum associated with the spin of the particles, without net charge transfer. This effect constitutes the spin analog of the BPVE and is especially relevant in systems where exchange interactions or spin-orbit coupling generate an effective asymmetry between opposite spin configurations.

The formal description of the spin photovoltaic effect requires introducing the spin

current operator, defined, analogously to the charge current operator, from the continuity equation for the spin density. If we denote by S_i^α the spin operator in the α direction and by $j_i^{S,\alpha}$ the corresponding flow between sites i and $i + 1$, the continuity equation takes the form:

$$\frac{dS_i^\alpha}{dt} + \left(j_{i+1}^{S,\alpha} - j_i^{S,\alpha} \right) = 0. \quad (2)$$

This relation expresses the local conservation of spin angular momentum in the absence of dissipation and makes it possible to establish a formal parallelism with the conservation of electric charge. A more complete expression will be provided in the chapter corresponding to the spin current.

In spin systems, such as the Heisenberg model with alternating exchange, modulations in the couplings and the breaking of inversion symmetry open the possibility of generating optically induced spin currents without the need for large static magnetic fields. Such nonlinear responses can be interpreted as a purely quantum version of the photovoltaic effect, in which the transported quantity is not charge but spin. These types of phenomena, currently the subject of intense research, offer a conceptual bridge between the physics of topological materials and spintronics [28].

1.6 Objectives of the Master's Thesis

With all this in mind, we can now present the main objectives of this Master's project. The first will be to be able to understand and simulate a Hamiltonian of the Heisenberg model with alternating exchange in order to see whether it is possible to obtain the *shift current* discussed in the previous section. For this purpose, the QuSpin Python library will be used, which will be discussed in more detail later.

Secondly, the aim will be to put quantum algorithms into practice, more specifically the Variational Quantum Eigensolver, in order to assess how effective they are in the context of many-body problem simulation compared with purely classical algorithms.

2 Methods for Solving the Heisenberg Model with Alternating Exchange

2.1 Diagonalization and properties of the model

The first method to be studied will be the easiest to implement, since it only involves the diagonalization of the Hamiltonian matrix of the system in order to obtain the corresponding eigenvalues and eigenfunctions. For this purpose, the QuSpin package [38] in Python will be used, which already includes optimized algorithms for this type of problem. Specifically, QuSpin is an open-source Python package for exact diagonalization and quantum dynamics of many-body systems of bosons, fermions, and spins in an arbitrary manner. QuSpin allows the use of various symmetries (defined by the user) for systems on one-dimensional and higher-dimensional lattices, time evolution (real or imaginary) under user-specified driving protocols, restricted Hilbert spaces, and parallel sparse linear algebra tools.

The procedure will be very simple. First, values will be assigned to the corresponding variables: N will be the number of spins, the dominant exchange will always be taken as $J_1 = 1$ and the alternating exchange as J_2 , with $J_1 = 1 \geq J_2 \geq 0$. It will be decided whether PBC (Periodic Boundary Conditions) are used, this being a positive boolean variable if they are used and negative if OBC (Open Boundary Conditions) are used, in addition to another boolean variable to indicate whether the chain starts with a strong interaction (J_1) or a weak one (J_2).

The next step will be to generate the matrix that represents the Hamiltonian of the Heisenberg model, which has been defined in (1). However, it is not possible to directly introduce the spin operators \mathbf{S} into the program, so it is necessary to apply some operator identity such that:

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^N J_i \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1} = \sum_{i=1}^N J_i (S_i^x S_{i+1}^x + S_i^y S_{i+1}^y + S_i^z S_{i+1}^z) \quad (3)$$

Moreover, due to the simplicity of the computational calculations and the nature of the operators S^x and S^y , the following equivalence with the raising and lowering operators S^+ and S^- is also used, where $S^x = \frac{1}{2}(S^+ + S^-)$, $S^y = \frac{1}{2i}(S^+ - S^-)$, obtaining:

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^N J_i \left[\frac{1}{2} (S_i^+ S_{i+1}^- + S_i^- S_{i+1}^+) + S_i^z S_{i+1}^z \right] \quad (4)$$

This form is particularly useful in practice, since the operators S^\pm act as raising and lowering operators that exchange neighboring spins without altering the total magnetization,

$$S_i^+ S_{i+1}^- |\uparrow_i \downarrow_{i+1}\rangle = |\downarrow_i \uparrow_{i+1}\rangle, \quad S_i^- S_{i+1}^+ |\downarrow_i \uparrow_{i+1}\rangle = |\uparrow_i \downarrow_{i+1}\rangle.$$

In this way, the conservation of the total magnetization S_{tot}^z becomes explicit, since $[H, S_{\text{tot}}^z] = 0$.

In libraries such as QuSpin [38], this decomposition is used to efficiently construct the Hamiltonian by means of interaction lists such as ["+-", bonds_xy], ["-+", bonds_xy], and ["zz", bonds], which directly implement the terms of the previous form. In the case of spins $S = \frac{1}{2}$, the operators are represented as $S^\alpha = \frac{1}{2}\sigma^\alpha$, where σ^α are the Pauli matrices.

The next step is to diagonalize this matrix in order to obtain the energies and eigenfunctions of the Hamiltonian states. For this purpose, the functions `eigh` and `eigsh` from QuSpin are used. The former performs a purely classical diagonalization; however, as discussed in the introduction of this work, this function with the available computational resources is only useful for chains with a number of spins N smaller than 14, due to the problem of dimensionality. For this reason, `eigsh` is also employed, which uses the Lanczos algorithm from the SciPy library to obtain the data. The Lanczos method is an iterative algorithm that allows one to obtain the extreme eigenvalues and eigenvectors of a Hermitian matrix without fully diagonalizing it. At each step, a subspace is generated from an initial vector and a much smaller tridiagonal matrix is constructed, whose diagonalization approximates the eigenvalues of the original system. In this way, the method allows the lowest energy levels of the Hamiltonian to be calculated with high precision, making it ideal for large systems. In QuSpin, the function `eigsh` implements this procedure through the *SciPy* library, allowing chains with $N > 14$ to be treated.

With all this, we can now obtain the results that can be seen in the different cases of the following subsections.

2.1.1 Heisenberg dimer

The Heisenberg dimer with spins $S = \frac{1}{2}$ is one of the simplest quantum systems that exhibits non-trivial correlations and an energy level structure that depends on the exchange interaction. It is composed of two particles with spin $\frac{1}{2}$, coupled through the interaction described in the Heisenberg model. Despite its simplicity, this system will serve to understand key concepts such as entanglement, multiplet structure, and the magnetic behavior of more complex materials and structures within the same model. Furthermore,

as will be seen later, the AEHM can be understood as a sequence of dimers coupled to each other by an interaction; therefore, the first step in studying the general model will be to analyze what happens for an isolated dimer.

We know that the Hamiltonian of the system, in the absence of a magnetic field, is given by

$$\hat{H} = J \vec{S}_1 \cdot \vec{S}_2 \quad (5)$$

where \vec{S}_1 and \vec{S}_2 are the total spin operators of each particle, and J is the coupling constant.

The Hilbert space of the system has dimension 4, corresponding to the possible combinations of the two spins $\uparrow\uparrow, \uparrow\downarrow, \downarrow\uparrow, \downarrow\downarrow$. These combinations can be reorganized into a basis of states with well-defined symmetry: one singlet state and one triplet. The singlet is an entangled state with total spin zero,

$$|S = 0, M = 0\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle)$$

while the triplets correspond to total spin one with three possible projections:

$$\begin{aligned} |S = 1, M = 1\rangle &= |\uparrow\uparrow\rangle \\ |S = 1, M = 0\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle + |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle) \\ |S = 1, M = -1\rangle &= |\downarrow\downarrow\rangle \end{aligned}$$

By diagonalizing the Hamiltonian in this basis, the energy spectrum is obtained: the singlet has energy $E_s = -\frac{3}{4}J$, while the three triplets are degenerate with energy $E_t = \frac{1}{4}J$. Therefore, in the antiferromagnetic case ($J > 0$), the ground state is the singlet and there exists an energy gap of J between the singlet and the triplets. In the ferromagnetic case ($J < 0$), the triplet becomes the ground state.

When an external magnetic field \vec{B} is applied (for example, along the z direction), the Hamiltonian is modified as

$$\hat{H} = J \vec{S}_1 \cdot \vec{S}_2 - g\mu_B B(S_1^z + S_2^z) \quad (6)$$

where g is the gyromagnetic factor and μ_B is the Bohr magneton. This additional term commutes with S_{tot}^2 , so the singlet/triplet basis still diagonalizes the Hamiltonian. The singlet is not affected by the field since it has $M = 0$, while the triplets split linearly

in energy according to their magnetization M ,

$$E_s = -\frac{3}{4}J, \quad E_{t,M} = \frac{1}{4}J - g\mu_B B M, \quad M \in \{-1, 0, +1\}.$$

This implies that, in a plot of E versus B , the singlet level appears as a horizontal line, the triplet with $M = 0$ is also horizontal but shifted upward, and the triplets with $M = \pm 1$ have slopes $\mp g\mu_B$. For $J > 0$, the state $|1, +1\rangle$ decreases with B and crosses the singlet at a critical value $B_c = \frac{J}{g\mu_B}$, beyond which the system is in a polarized ground state. These checks can be performed numerically in a straightforward way.

2.1.2 Finite Heisenberg chain

The next case to be studied is the finite Heisenberg chain. Instead of having only two interacting spins, we now consider a one-dimensional system formed by spin-1/2 particles coupled through an antiferromagnetic exchange interaction. In contrast to the two-spin case, where the energy-level structure is simple and can be solved in an elementary way, increasing the number of particles gives rise to characteristic collective phenomena. Among these, the properties of the ground state and the nature of the excitations stand out, both of which depend strongly on the number of sites as well as on the boundary conditions imposed on the system.

One of the most characteristic phenomena of finite Heisenberg chains is the so-called even-odd effect, which reflects how the parity of the number of spins N determines the structure of the ground state of the system. This result was formalized by Lieb and Mattis in 1962 [26], who proved that for a one-dimensional antiferromagnetic system with spins $S = \frac{1}{2}$ and homogeneous couplings, if N is even, the ground state has total spin $S_{\text{tot}} = 0$, i.e., it is a singlet. If N is odd, the ground state has total spin $S_{\text{tot}} = \frac{1}{2}$, corresponding to a doublet.

This behavior can be understood intuitively by noting that, under antiferromagnetic coupling, each spin tends to pair antiparallel with its neighbor. When the number of sites is even, all spins can be completely paired, leading to a minimum-energy state with no net magnetization. By contrast, if the number of sites is odd, one spin remains unpaired, which causes the system to exhibit a nonzero total magnetic moment.

The following figure illustrates this phenomenon for chains with periodic boundary conditions (PBC). The plot shows the total spin inferred from $\langle \mathbf{S}^2 \rangle$ as a function of the number of sites N . A clear alternation between $S_{\text{tot}} = 0$ and $S_{\text{tot}} = \frac{1}{2}$ is observed, depending on whether N is even or odd.

Figure 1: First calculations of the Heisenberg model for a finite chain. The left panel shows the total spin of the ground state as a function of the chain length N , highlighting the characteristic even–odd effect of antiferromagnetic chains with $S = \frac{1}{2}$ under open boundary conditions (OBC). The right panel shows the scaling of the energy difference between the ground state and the first excited state as a function of $1/N$ for chains with PBC, together with a linear fit of the form $\text{gap}(N) = a(1/N) + b$.

The complementary analysis carried out to characterize finite chains consists of studying the dependence of the energy gap on the chain length. The gap is defined as the difference between the first excited state and the ground state. In the previous figure, the gap measured in units of J is shown as a function of $1/N$ for chains with periodic boundary conditions (PBC). The points correspond to numerical values obtained for different values of N , and the dashed line represents a linear fit in $1/N$.

The linear fit shown in the figure has the form

$$\text{gap}(N) \approx a \left(\frac{1}{N} \right) + b, \quad (7)$$

and the parameters obtained from the fit (shown in the plot legend) are approximately

$$a \approx 3.9458, \quad b \approx 2.4448 \times 10^{-2}.$$

These values indicate that, within the range of system sizes analyzed, the dependence on $1/N$ is well captured by a dominant term proportional to $1/N$ plus a small constant contribution. A quadratic term was also tested but was found to be negligible compared to the value of a . Moreover, it is worth mentioning that if this plot were performed for an infinite chain, i.e., $N \rightarrow \infty$, the value of b would ultimately tend to zero and, consequently, the gap would vanish. In addition, from [2] and [29] one can obtain a bound a' for the

coefficient a in Eq. 7, namely $a' = \pi^2/2 \sim 4.93$, with $a' \geq a$, which is indeed satisfied by the present calculation.

These results have several important physical implications. In the thermodynamic limit ($N \rightarrow \infty$), the energy difference between states of different parity tends to vanish, reflecting that the system approaches a global singlet state, in agreement with Bethe's classical result (1931) and with [2].

The final topic we address is the calculation of the local expectation value of the spin. Using the results obtained with QuSpin, we obtain the following plots:

Figure 2: The figure shows the local magnetization profiles $\langle S_i^z \rangle$ for Heisenberg chains of different lengths N under periodic (PBC) and open (OBC) boundary conditions. For odd values of N (e.g., $N = 9, 15$), the ground state corresponds to a doublet with total spin $S_{\text{tot}} = 1/2$, which is reflected in a nonzero local magnetization distributed along the chain. In the OBC case, this magnetization exhibits a well-defined alternating pattern (Néel-like order), whereas for PBC a regular distribution is also observed, consistent with the presence of an uncompensated net spin.

In contrast to the previous cases, the first thing to note is that for even values of N (e.g., $N = 10, 20$), the ground state is a singlet ($S_{\text{tot}} = 0$). As a result, the symmetry of the problem enforces $\langle S_i^z \rangle = 0$. Therefore, if one plots the local magnetization for even N , it is numerically verified that it vanishes at all sites, both for PBC and OBC.

These results clearly illustrate the even–odd effect in finite chains: the parity of the number of spins determines whether the ground state exhibits local magnetization, and how this magnetization is modulated by the boundary conditions. With this, we conclude the analysis of the standard Heisenberg model and move on to introducing a model with alternating exchange, which gives rise to different properties from those observed so far.

2.1.3 Heisenberg chain with alternating exchange

The Heisenberg chain with alternating exchange, also known as the dimerized chain, constitutes a natural extension of the models discussed previously. The dimer, which consists of only two spins coupled via an antiferromagnetic exchange interaction, allows for a simple introduction to the physics of singlet and triplet state formation, as well as the notion of a well-defined excitation gap equal to the coupling constant. On the other hand, the uniform chain, in which all bonds have the same exchange strength, exhibits a very different behavior: as the number of spins increases, the competition between collective interactions leads to a critical, gapless system.

The chain with alternating exchange lies between these two extremes. Recall that its Hamiltonian can be written as in Eq. 1, where the couplings J_i alternate between two values, J_1 and J_2 . In the limit $J_1 = J_2$, the uniform chain is recovered, while for $J_2 \rightarrow 0$ the system fragments into a set of independent dimers with a gap equal to J_2 . Thus, by varying the ratio J_2/J_1 , one can continuously tune between a critical gapless regime and a regime of decoupled dimers with a finite gap. This makes the alternating-exchange chain an ideal testbed for studying gap opening induced by dimerization and the effects of edges under open boundary conditions.

A relevant aspect is the role played by the chain terminations. If an open chain ends with a strong bond, the edge spins are paired. By contrast, if it ends with a weak bond, the edge spins remain nearly free. From the numerical results obtained, two checks can be performed to characterize the behavior of the gap under these termination and boundary conditions.

First, under periodic boundary conditions (PBC), the system has no edges and therefore no states localized at the ends. In this case, when $J_2 \rightarrow 0$, the system decomposes into a set of independent dimers, and the gap takes the value J_1 , in perfect agreement with the strongly dimerized limit. This has been numerically verified.

Second, for chains with open boundary conditions (OBC) terminated by a weak bond (J_2), it is observed that the gap decreases with chain length more rapidly as the ratio

J_1/J_2 increases. This effect arises because the weakly coupled edge spins generate edge states whose energies approach the ground-state energy exponentially as the degree of dimerization increases.

Figure 3: Decay of the energy gap with chain length N for open boundary conditions (OBC) terminated by a weak bond (J_1) in the alternating-exchange Heisenberg model. Results are shown for different ratios J_1/J_2 . The gap is seen to decrease exponentially with N , with a faster decay for larger values of J_1/J_2 .

Beyond the spectral analysis, it is instructive to examine the spin–spin correlations between neighboring sites, $\langle \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1} \rangle$, which provide a direct measure of the degree of dimerization in the system.

In the following figure, one observes that in the limit $J_2 \rightarrow 0$, correlations on the strong bonds J_1 tend toward the value $-3/4$, characteristic of a singlet formed by a pair of spins, while correlations on the weak bonds J_2 vanish, reflecting the absence of coupling between dimers. This behavior confirms that the ground state in this regime can be described as a set of nearly independent dimers.

As the ratio J_1/J_2 decreases, correlations on the weak bonds become more negative and those on the strong bonds become less pronounced, reducing the alternation between them. Finally, in the limit $J_1 = J_2$, the correlations become homogeneous and reach the typical value of the uniform Heisenberg chain, $\langle \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1} \rangle \approx -0.44$, corresponding to a critical gapless system. This value is exactly known from the Bethe ansatz solution [27], where $\langle \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1} \rangle = 1/4 - \ln(2) \approx -0.44$.

Figure 4: Nearest-neighbor spin–spin correlation profiles, $\langle \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1} \rangle$, for extreme values of the ratio J_2/J_1 in a Heisenberg chain with $N = 18$ and periodic boundary conditions. The characteristic alternation of the dimerized phase and the tendency toward uniform values as the critical limit $J_1 = J_2$ is approached are clearly visible. The red and green dashed lines indicate the theoretical values $-3/4$ and 0 corresponding to the independent-dimer limit.

Nearest-neighbor spin–spin correlations provide a clear local signature of dimerization in the bulk of the chain. As the ratio J_2/J_1 is reduced, correlations on the strong bonds become increasingly negative, approaching the singlet value, while correlations on the weak bonds are progressively suppressed. This behavior reflects the tendency of the system to form nearly independent dimers and is consistent with the opening of a finite bulk gap in the dimerized regime.

Nevertheless, bulk correlations alone do not fully determine the low-energy properties of finite chains. When open boundary conditions are considered, the way in which the alternating pattern terminates at the edges becomes essential. Even in a strongly dimerized phase, a weak-bond termination can leave spins at the chain ends only weakly coupled to the rest of the system. These edge spins can then generate low-energy states within the bulk gap, significantly affecting the excitation spectrum and its dependence on system size.

For this reason, the evolution of the energy gap must be analyzed in conjunction with boundary conditions and termination patterns. In the following figures, we study how the ground-state energy gap evolves as a function of the exchange ratio and chain length for different terminations, revealing the crucial role played by edge states and providing a clear connection between bulk dimerization and boundary-induced low-energy excitations.

Figure 5: Evolution of the ground-state energy gap as a function of the ratio J_2/J_1 for the Heisenberg chain with strong termination under open boundary conditions. Results are shown for chains of even and odd length. As $J_2 \rightarrow J_1$, the system approaches the uniform gapless limit, while increasing dimerization (smaller J_2) leads to a progressively larger gap. In this case, the edge spins are paired through strong bonds, so that no quasi-free edge states appear and the gap remains finite throughout the range $0.3 \leq J_2/J_1 \leq 1$.

Figure 6: Dependence of the energy gap on the ratio J_2/J_1 for the chain with weak termination under open boundary conditions. Results are shown for even and odd values of N . In contrast to the previous case, the edge spins are not paired, leading to the appearance of states localized at the chain ends and to an effective closing of the gap for intermediate values of J_2 . This behavior reflects the presence of topological edge modes, which are particularly visible in chains of odd length.

Figures 5 and 6 highlight the crucial role played by termination conditions in the alternating-exchange Heisenberg chain. In the case of strong termination, the final bonds pair the edge spins, which suppresses the appearance of topological states and maintains a finite energy gap even in the strongly dimerized regime. By contrast, weak termination leaves uncompensated spins at the chain ends, favoring the emergence of edge modes and an apparent closing of the gap as J_2 is reduced. This contrast provides a clear illustration of the bulk–boundary correspondence in dimerized systems: while the bulk continues to be described by gapped excitations, the edges can host quasi-free degrees of freedom that determine the effective topology of the system. Moreover, the difference between even and odd chains reinforces the dependence of magnetic and topological properties on the parity of the number of sites, a distinctive feature of the alternating Heisenberg model. These results provide clear evidence of the transition between trivial and nontrivial topological phases, analogous to that observed in other models such as the SSH model [14].

Beyond the behavior of the gap, the localization of edge modes can be directly observed in the spatial profile of the local magnetization. To this end, the following plots illustrate how the expectation value $\langle S_z \rangle$ is distributed along the chain.

Figure 7: Profile of $\langle S^z \rangle$ in a Heisenberg chain with $S = 1$ and $S_z = +1$, of length $N = 20$, terminated with a strong link. The values $J_1/J_2 = 0.01$ (left panel) and $J_1/J_2 = 0.3$ (right panel) are considered. The solid line represents a sinusoidal fit of the form $A \cdot \sin(\pi n/N)$, where A is $\max_i(S_{z,i})$ and n labels the sites of the chain. This function captures the spatial variation of the bulk magnetization. In addition, one can observe the formation of dimer pairs along the chain, with a jump in $\langle S^z \rangle$ across each of them. This behavior arises because $J_1 \ll J_2$. Comparing both cases, when $J_1/J_2 = 0.3$ the profile increasingly resembles that of the standard Heisenberg model, where it takes the form of a Néel-like pattern.

Figure 8: Profile of $\langle S_z \rangle$ in a Heisenberg chain with $S = 1$ and $S_z = +1$, of length $N = 20$, terminated with a weak bond. A pronounced accumulation of magnetization at the chain ends is observed, providing clear evidence of localized edge modes. As in the previous figure, the right panel corresponds to $J_1/J_2 = 0.3$ and the left panel to $J_1/J_2 = 0.01$. From the comparison, it is evident that the larger the difference between the strong and weak exchange couplings, the more pronounced the accumulation of magnetization at the chain ends becomes.

Figure 7 shows the $\langle S_z \rangle$ profile for a chain with strong-bond termination. The local magnetization follows a sinusoidal profile typical of a bulk state, with no accumulation at the edges. This behavior is consistent with the absence of edge modes for this type of termination. By contrast, Figure 8, corresponding to a chain with weak-bond termination, exhibits a clear accumulation of magnetization at the chain ends, indicating the presence of localized edge modes.

A notable aspect of the spatial profile of $\langle S_i^z \rangle$ shown in Fig. 7 is that, in the regime of strong exchange alternation ($J_2 \gg J_1$), the state with $S = 1$ and $S_z = +1$ is distributed along the chain with a clearly sinusoidal weight, analogous to the ground-state wavefunction of a particle confined in an infinite potential well.

In this limit, spins coupled by J_2 form nearly independent dimers, such that a triplet excitation acting on one of these dimers can propagate along the chain through the weak bonds J_1 . This excitation therefore acquires the character of an itinerant quasiparticle. The quantity $\langle S_i^z \rangle$ plays the role of a probability density on each bond, while the chain ends act as boundary conditions that confine this quasiparticle within an effective infinite potential well. The excellent agreement between the numerical profile and the sinusoidal fit $\langle S_i^z \rangle \propto \sin\left(\frac{\pi i}{N}\right)$ is not accidental, but rather constitutes evidence that, in the strong-bond regime, the alternating-exchange Heisenberg model can be described by an effective single-particle theory, where the triplon (the $S = 1$ excitation) propagates along the chain as a confined mode with behavior analogous to the ground state of an infinite potential well.

2.2 Variational Quantum Eigensolver

We now consider a completely different strategy to obtain the ground state of the system: the use of quantum algorithms applied to the alternating-exchange Heisenberg model studied in this work. In particular, we employ a hybrid quantum–classical algorithm known as the *Variational Quantum Eigensolver* (VQE), specifically designed to estimate the ground-state energy of many-body quantum systems. The main motivation for exploring this type of technology is the possibility of overcoming the scalability problems faced by the classical methods discussed in the introduction, which will be addressed in greater detail in the section devoted to VQE itself [8, 20, 39].

A key aspect that facilitates the use of quantum techniques in this context is the convenience of working with spin-1/2 systems, due to their mathematical isomorphism with the qubits used in quantum computing. Both share a two-dimensional Hilbert space, which allows for a natural identification of the states $\{|\uparrow\rangle, |\downarrow\rangle\}$ with the computational basis states $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$. Under this correspondence, spin operators can be written as

$$S^\alpha = \frac{1}{2} \sigma^\alpha, \quad \alpha \in \{x, y, z\},$$

where σ^α denotes the Pauli matrices acting on the qubits of a real quantum computer. This equivalence implies that any spin-1/2 Hamiltonian can be directly mapped onto a sum of tensor products of Pauli matrices, enabling its implementation on quantum hardware via the variational VQE algorithm. Thanks to this isomorphism, the system Hamiltonian can be encoded as a linear combination of Pauli operators, allowing a parametrized quantum device to evaluate expectation values of the energy and perform the variational search for the ground state.

Structurally, VQE is based on the construction of a parametrized quantum circuit, or *ansatz*, which generates a quantum state depending on a set of variational parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. This ansatz is applied to an initial reference state $|\psi_{\text{ref}}\rangle$, producing a variational state

$$|\psi(\boldsymbol{\theta})\rangle = U(\boldsymbol{\theta}) |\psi_{\text{ref}}\rangle.$$

In our case, the reference state is chosen to be the singlet, since the alternating-exchange Heisenberg model can be understood as a sequence of dimers whose ground state is precisely a product of singlets. The circuit is then executed on a quantum device to estimate the expectation value of the energy,

$$E(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \langle \psi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) | H | \psi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \rangle,$$

which depends explicitly on the variational parameters. This value is obtained through quantum measurements on the hardware, while a classical optimizer updates the parameters θ with the goal of minimizing $E(\theta)$. This process is repeated iteratively until the energy converges to a minimum, yielding an approximation to the ground-state energy of the system.

The general structure of the method is illustrated in the following schematic:

Figure 9: Schematic representation of the VQE workflow. The figure has been adapted from [40].

This hybrid approach is particularly well suited for current noisy intermediate-scale quantum (NISQ) devices, as it requires low-depth circuits and delegates the most computationally demanding part of the optimization to a classical processor. Moreover, its flexible structure allows the ansatz to be tailored to the specific features of the physical system, making VQE a promising tool for the study of spin Hamiltonians such as the alternating-exchange Heisenberg model analyzed in this project.

2.3 Dynamical evolution of the model

Once the static properties of the model have been studied using multiple methods and the corresponding eigenvalues and eigenstates have been obtained, the next step is to analyze the time evolution of the system. In addition, an external perturbation is

introduced and the Hamiltonian is allowed to evolve up to a final time T , which is varied for each simulation.

Since the goal is to break the global symmetry of the system, the external perturbation is introduced in the form of a localized AC drive, given by

$$H_{AC}(t) = b \cos(\omega t) S_1^x, \quad (8)$$

where b is the amplitude of the perturbation and ω its frequency. This perturbation is applied exclusively to the first site of the chain and acts only on the S^x operator. In other words, it corresponds to an oscillating magnetic field applied locally to the spin located at site 1 of the chain. This choice is not arbitrary: in the Heisenberg model, a global perturbation of the same form commutes with the total spin operator of the system, $\vec{S}_{\text{tot}} = \sum_i \vec{S}_i$. Since the Heisenberg Hamiltonian also conserves the total spin, if H_{AC} shares this symmetry, the perturbation cannot induce transitions between states with different total spin quantum numbers. This strongly limits its dynamical effect and prevents the selective excitation of the relevant states in the dimerized chain. By contrast, using a local perturbation such as that in Eq. (8) explicitly breaks the symmetry associated with total spin conservation, allowing for much richer excitation dynamics, which are essential for the subsequent analysis.

In addition, the system presents a problem related to state degeneracies. As is well known, singlet states are associated with a single energy level, whereas triplet and higher-spin states consist of multiple degenerate states sharing the same energy. It is therefore necessary to distinguish these states in order to analyze quantities such as state occupations or the local spin expectation values $\langle S_i^z \rangle$. For this reason, a Zeeman effect is introduced in the form of a magnetic field applied along the z direction, thus defining a privileged direction in space. This field is chosen to be sufficiently large to lift the degeneracies in the energy spectrum, yet small enough so that the global properties of the Hamiltonian remain essentially unaffected. This term takes the form

$$H_{Zee} = \sum_{i=1}^N h_z S_i^z. \quad (9)$$

That is, a global term acting on the S^z operator of each spin is applied. Throughout this work, the value $h_z = 10^{-4}$ is typically used.

With all these ingredients, the full time-dependent Hamiltonian that governs the dy-

namics of the system is given by

$$H_{\text{total}}(t) = \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^N J_i \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1}}_{\text{Heisenberg}} + \underbrace{b \cos(\omega t) S_1^x}_{\text{AC}} + \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^N h_z S_i^z}_{\text{Zeeman}}. \quad (10)$$

From a computational point of view, this setup can be straightforwardly implemented in QUSPIN using the time-dependent functionality of the library. Once all the required operators and Hamiltonians have been defined, the system is evolved using the `evolve` function. The initial condition is taken to be the ground-state wavefunction previously computed, and the simulation times are specified. The `iterate` option is enabled so that the wavefunction is stored at each time step, which is useful for subsequent calculations.

The `evolve` function numerically solves the time-dependent Schrödinger equation by applying the time-evolution operator to the initial state. In practical terms, it takes the initial state $|\psi(0)\rangle$ as input and returns the evolved state $|\psi(t)\rangle$ at each requested time, computed from the differential equation

$$\frac{d}{dt} |\psi(t)\rangle = -i H(t) |\psi(t)\rangle,$$

using the RK-DOP853 numerical method, an embedded Runge–Kutta scheme of order 8(5,3) [38].

Once the wavefunction has been computed for all time instants, several time-dependent analyses can be performed. The system most extensively studied in this project, due to its low computational cost and conceptual simplicity, is the tetramer. Moreover, the analysis is generally carried out in the strong dimerization regime, where $J_1 \gg J_2$. In this case, the system consists of two dimers coupled by an interaction J_2 , as illustrated in Fig. 10.

Figure 10: Schematic representation of the system considered. It corresponds to a Heisenberg tetramer with alternating exchange couplings, starting with a strong bond (J_1) and periodic boundary conditions.

In this context, the spectrum consists of two singlet states, three triplet states, and one quintuplet, yielding a total of 16 possible energy levels. Among these, the singlet corresponding to the alternating spin configuration is the ground state, while one of the triplets constitutes the first excited state. As discussed previously, the energy difference between these two states defines the gap of the system. For each pair of values (J_1, J_2) , a different energy spectrum is obtained. Nevertheless, at $t = 0$ the following general ordering of states by increasing energy can be established:

$$\text{Singlet 1} \leq \text{Triplet 1} \leq \text{Triplet 2} \leq \text{Singlet 2} \leq \text{Triplet 3} \leq \text{Quintuplet}. \quad (11)$$

To study the response of the tetramer to an external driving field, it is useful to employ time-dependent perturbation theory, in particular the Dyson series [19]. This formalism allows one to compute transition probabilities between energy levels when the system is driven periodically, and provides criteria to identify the ranges of amplitude b and frequency ω for which the dynamics becomes significant.

Consider the Hamiltonian in the absence of the Zeeman term,

$$H(t) = H_0 + V(t), \quad (12)$$

where the unperturbed Hamiltonian satisfies $H_0|n\rangle = E_n|n\rangle$, and the periodic perturbation is given by

$$V(t) = b \cos(\omega t) S_1^x. \quad (13)$$

In the interaction picture, the perturbation takes the form

$$V_I(t) = e^{iH_0 t} V(t) e^{-iH_0 t}. \quad (14)$$

The time-evolution operator in this representation is given by the Dyson series,

$$U_I(t, 0) = T \exp\left(-i \int_0^t dt' V_I(t')\right) = 1 - i \int_0^t dt_1 V_I(t_1) - \int_0^t dt_1 \int_0^{t_1} dt_2 V_I(t_1) V_I(t_2) + \dots, \quad (15)$$

where T denotes time ordering. If the system is initially prepared in the ground state $|\psi(0)\rangle = |0\rangle$, the transition amplitude to an excited state $|n\rangle$ at time t is

$$c_n(t) = \langle n | U_I(t, 0) | 0 \rangle. \quad (16)$$

Truncating the Dyson series to first order yields

$$c_n^{(1)}(t) = -i \int_0^t dt' \langle n | V_I(t') | 0 \rangle. \quad (17)$$

Using

$$\langle n|V_I(t')|0\rangle = e^{i(E_n - E_0)t'} \langle n|V(t')|0\rangle, \quad (18)$$

and substituting the explicit form of the perturbation,

$$V(t') = b \cos(\omega t') S_1^x, \quad (19)$$

one obtains

$$c_n^{(1)}(t) = -ib \langle n|S_1^x|0\rangle \int_0^t dt' e^{i\Delta_n t'} \cos(\omega t'), \quad \Delta_n = E_n - E_0. \quad (20)$$

Using the identity

$$\cos(\omega t') = \frac{1}{2} (e^{i\omega t'} + e^{-i\omega t'}), \quad (21)$$

the integral splits into two contributions:

$$c_n^{(1)}(t) = -i\frac{b}{2} \langle n|S_x|0\rangle \left[\int_0^t dt' e^{i(\Delta_n + \omega)t'} + \int_0^t dt' e^{i(\Delta_n - \omega)t'} \right]. \quad (22)$$

Each term is of the form

$$\int_0^t e^{i\alpha t'} dt' = \frac{e^{i\alpha t} - 1}{i\alpha} = e^{i\alpha t/2} \frac{2 \sin(\alpha t/2)}{\alpha}. \quad (23)$$

Substituting this result, the amplitude becomes

$$c_n^{(1)}(t) = b \langle n|S_x|0\rangle \left[e^{i(\Delta_n + \omega)t/2} \frac{\sin[(\Delta_n + \omega)t/2]}{\Delta_n + \omega} + e^{i(\Delta_n - \omega)t/2} \frac{\sin[(\Delta_n - \omega)t/2]}{\Delta_n - \omega} \right]. \quad (24)$$

The first term oscillates rapidly and is typically much smaller than the second. Within the rotating-wave approximation (RWA), it can be neglected, leading to

$$c_n^{(1)}(t) \approx b \langle n|S_x|0\rangle e^{i(\Delta_n - \omega)t/2} \frac{\sin[(\Delta_n - \omega)t/2]}{\Delta_n - \omega}. \quad (25)$$

The transition probability to the excited state $|n\rangle$ is therefore

$$P_{0 \rightarrow n}(t) \approx |c_n^{(1)}(t)|^2 \approx b^2 |\langle n|S_x|0\rangle|^2 \frac{\sin^2[(\Delta_n - \omega)t/2]}{(\Delta_n - \omega)^2}. \quad (26)$$

$$P_{0 \rightarrow n}(t) \approx \left[\frac{bt}{2} |\langle n|S_x|0\rangle| \operatorname{sinc}[(\Delta_n - \omega)t/2] \right]^2. \quad (27)$$

Throughout this derivation, units with $\hbar = 1$ have been used. This first-order approximation is valid only for short simulation times and for perturbation amplitudes b small

compared to the energy gap. Nevertheless, it provides valuable insight into the resonance structure and the system response to the external drive. In the limit $t \rightarrow \infty$, one recovers Fermi's golden rule [19].

An alternative description can be obtained by considering a two-level approximation, in which only two states are dynamically active. Applying the rotating-wave approximation in this case leads to the well-known result [32]

$$P_{0 \rightarrow n}(t) \approx \frac{\Omega_R^2}{\Omega_R^2 + \delta^2} \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega t}{2} \right), \quad (28)$$

where $\Omega_R = b|\langle n|S_x|0\rangle|$, $\delta = \omega - \Delta_n$, and $\Omega = \sqrt{\Omega_R^2 - \delta^2}$. In resonance ($\omega \simeq \Delta_n$), one has $\delta = 0$ and $\Omega = \Omega_R$, yielding

$$P_{0 \rightarrow n}(t) \approx \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_R t}{2} \right). \quad (29)$$

Considering ω as the control parameter, both expressions show that the transition probability reaches a maximum when the driving frequency matches the energy gap, $\omega \simeq \Delta_n$. Away from resonance, the probability decays as $(\Delta_n - \omega)^{-2}$, and the system response rapidly diminishes. The amplitude b directly controls the overall transition probability and determines the effective width of the resonance. For small values of b , transitions occur only in a narrow frequency window around $\omega = \Delta_n$, whereas increasing b broadens the resonance and may induce nonlinear effects.

This behavior can be directly verified by computing the populations of the energy eigenstates and the expectation value of the energy as functions of time. Given the time-dependent wavefunction, the state populations are obtained as $P_n = |\langle \psi_n | \psi(t) \rangle|^2$, and the energy as $E(t) = \langle \psi(t) | H | \psi(t) \rangle$. By sweeping the driving frequency ω and evaluating, for each value, the maximum population reached during the simulation time, $\max_t |\langle \psi_n | \psi(t) \rangle|^2$, the resonance curves shown in Fig. 11 are obtained.

In general, the terms *activity* or *response* of the system will be used to refer to the probability that transitions between states occur, which will be relevant for the following section. To this end, the population of each state is represented as a function of time in the next figures.

Figure 11: Resonance curves for $b = 0.1$ and $b = 0.05$. The quantities $\max_t(|\langle \psi_n | \psi(t) \rangle|^2)$ are computed while sweeping the driving frequency ω . For the blue curve, the calculations are performed with $\omega = \Delta_1$, i.e., the driving frequency is equal to the energy gap between the first triplet and the ground state. The green curve corresponds to calculations with $\omega = \Delta_2$, where the frequency matches the gap between the second triplet and the ground state. The analytical prediction is clearly confirmed: the maximum response of the system, corresponding to a transition to an excited state n , occurs when $\omega = \Delta_n$. In addition, a narrower resonance peak is observed for the smaller value of b .

Figure 12: Time evolution of the state populations for $J_1 = 1$, $J_2 = 0.3$, and $b = 0.1$. In the left panel, the driving frequency is set equal to the gap (Δ_1), while in the right panel it is set to $0.8\Delta_1$. The strong impact of resonance on the system dynamics is evident. When the system is off resonance, it remains almost entirely in the ground state, whereas under resonant driving there is a significant probability of populating the triplet states and the second singlet.

Figure 13: Time evolution of the state populations at resonance with $\omega = \Delta_1$ and $b = 0.1$, illustrating the effect of the ratio J_2/J_1 on the dynamics. The left panel corresponds to a weak dimerization regime with $J_2/J_1 = 0.8$, while the right panel shows the extreme dimerization regime with $J_2/J_1 = 0.01$. In the former case, clear Rabi oscillations can be observed, as discussed in [32]. In the latter, the dynamics becomes harder to predict due to the involvement of higher-energy states such as the quintuplet.

Figure 14: Time evolution of the state populations at resonance with $\omega = \Delta_1$ and $J_2/J_1 = 0.1$. In the left panel, the system is studied within the first-order approximation, i.e., for small values of t and b , confirming that the triplet-state probability grows linearly with time, as predicted by Eq. (26). In the right panel, the system is subjected to a very strong perturbation, leading to chaotic behavior and a highly active dynamics over the short time interval during which the tetramer is exposed to the drive.

From the figure 13, it can be seen that the population changes exhibit periodic, wave-like behavior. Although these oscillations become harder to resolve in the strong dimerization regime, it is useful to understand their origin and connect them with the analysis based on the Dyson series and the discussion presented in Ref. [32]. These oscillations are known as *Rabi oscillations*. They are most clearly observed in systems where only the ground singlet and the first triplet are effectively involved in the dynamics, which occurs when $J_1 \sim J_2$, i.e., in the weak dimerization regime. From Eq. (29), one can also extract the oscillation period $T = 4\pi/\Omega_R$, with $\Omega_R = b|\langle n|S_x|0\rangle|$.

In the last figure, a series of limiting cases are highlighted, corresponding to small values of t and b , and to the opposite regime where b becomes excessively large.

3 Results. Exploration of spin currents for the AEHM

One of the main objectives of this Master's thesis was to investigate whether a DC response can be obtained from an AC perturbation in this Heisenberg model. For this reason, the next step consists of measuring the spin current of the system. Moreover, once the time evolution of the state populations of the model has been studied, it is straightforward to construct operators to probe different physical properties. However, the first step is to determine the explicit form of the spin-current operator introduced in the introductory section. For any local quantity Q_i whose total sum $Q = \sum_i Q_i$ is a conserved magnitude, its time evolution must satisfy a continuity equation of the form

$$\frac{dQ_i}{dt} = -(\mathbf{j}_i - \mathbf{j}_{i-1}), \quad (30)$$

where \mathbf{j}_i represents the current associated with the flow of Q from site i to site $i + 1$.

In the case of spin, one takes $Q_i = S_i^z$. If the total spin $S^z = \sum_i S_i^z$ is conserved by the dynamics, the continuity equation reads

$$\frac{dS_i^z}{dt} = -(\mathbf{j}_i^z - \mathbf{j}_{i-1}^z). \quad (31)$$

Using the Heisenberg equation of motion,

$$\frac{dS_i^z}{dt} = i[H, S_i^z], \quad (32)$$

the explicit form of the spin-current operator \mathbf{j}_i^z is obtained by evaluating the commutator with the Hamiltonian. In this case,

$$H = \sum_i J_i (S_i^x S_{i+1}^x + S_i^y S_{i+1}^y + S_i^z S_{i+1}^z), \quad (33)$$

which corresponds to the one-dimensional isotropic Heisenberg Hamiltonian, with alternating couplings J_1 for odd i and J_2 for even i . In the commutator above, only the Hamiltonian terms acting on site i contribute, namely those associated with the bonds $(i - 1, i)$ and $(i, i + 1)$. Let us consider

$$\hat{h}_{i,i+1} = J_i (S_i^x S_{i+1}^x + S_i^y S_{i+1}^y + S_i^z S_{i+1}^z). \quad (34)$$

Since operators acting on different sites commute, one finds

$$[\hat{h}_{i,i+1}, S_i^z] = J_i ([S_i^x, S_i^z] S_{i+1}^x + [S_i^y, S_i^z] S_{i+1}^y + [S_i^z, S_i^z] S_{i+1}^z). \quad (35)$$

The commutation relations of the $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ algebra are

$$[S_i^x, S_i^z] = iS_i^y, \quad [S_i^y, S_i^z] = -iS_i^x, \quad [S_i^z, S_i^z] = 0, \quad (36)$$

which lead to

$$i[\hat{h}_{i,i+1}, S_i^z] = J_i(S_i^x S_{i+1}^y - S_i^y S_{i+1}^x). \quad (37)$$

The contribution from the bond $(i-1, i)$ yields the same expression with the opposite sign. Summing both contributions, one obtains

$$\frac{dS_i^z}{dt} = -(j_i^z - j_{i-1}^z), \quad j_i^z = J_i(S_i^x S_{i+1}^y - S_i^y S_{i+1}^x). \quad (38)$$

Using

$$S^x = \frac{1}{2}(S^+ + S^-), \quad S^y = \frac{1}{2i}(S^+ - S^-), \quad (39)$$

one finds

$$S_i^x S_{i+1}^y - S_i^y S_{i+1}^x = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2i} \right) [(S_i^+ + S_i^-)(S_{i+1}^+ - S_{i+1}^-) - (S_i^+ - S_i^-)(S_{i+1}^+ + S_{i+1}^-)]. \quad (40)$$

Grouping terms yields

$$S_i^x S_{i+1}^y - S_i^y S_{i+1}^x = \frac{1}{4i} (-2S_i^+ S_{i+1}^- + 2S_i^- S_{i+1}^+) = \frac{i}{2} (S_i^+ S_{i+1}^- - S_i^- S_{i+1}^+). \quad (41)$$

Therefore,

$$j_i^z = J_i(S_i^x S_{i+1}^y - S_i^y S_{i+1}^x) = J_i \frac{i}{2} (S_i^+ S_{i+1}^- - S_i^- S_{i+1}^+), \quad (42)$$

or equivalently,

$$j_i^z = \frac{iJ_i}{2} S_i^+ S_{i+1}^- - \frac{iJ_i}{2} S_i^- S_{i+1}^+. \quad (43)$$

Note that although the Hamiltonian used in the previous section included neither the driving term nor the global magnetic field, these additional terms do not affect the spin-spin correlations, and therefore the spin-current operator remains unchanged.

An important remark at this point concerns the role of the magnetic field in this calculation. The spin current is directly related to S^z , so what is actually being observed is the time evolution of the spin polarization. If there were no privileged direction, i.e., if the triplet states were fully degenerate, singlet-triplet transitions could not be distinguished. In the absence of a magnetic field, the triplet states $|\uparrow\uparrow\rangle$ and $|\downarrow\downarrow\rangle$ would be populated equally, so that a gain of “up” spin would be compensated by an equal gain of “down” spin. As a result, the expectation value of S^z would remain zero even while the system is actually changing its state. The magnetic field lifts this degeneracy and selects a preferred

direction, causing the populations of the different triplet components to evolve differently. Thanks to this effect, the spin current can be detected.

With all these elements in place, the first results shown in the following figure can be obtained.

Figure 15: Time evolution of the state populations, the local expectation value $\langle S^z \rangle$ at each spin, and the total spin current at resonance for a tetramer with $J_2/J_1 = 0.3$. These plots clearly show the strong correlation between the maxima and minima of the expected value of S^z and the population peaks of the first triplet, which is physically expected and supports the validity of the calculation. Moreover, the global spin current exhibits maxima and minima when the local $\langle S^z \rangle$ is close to zero, i.e., when transitions between states occur. A noticeable correlation is also observed between the minima of the current expectation value and the population of the second singlet.

The next step is to analyze what happens at each bond and to determine the spin current flowing through each link of the tetramer. For this purpose, it is useful to recall the structure shown in Fig. 10. The analysis can be focused on spins 1 and 3 in order to distinguish the current transmitted between dimers (bonds 1–4 and 2–3) from the spin current flowing within each dimer (bonds 1–2 and 3–4). The following figure illustrates this situation clearly.

Figure 16: Time evolution of the local expectation values $\langle S^z \rangle$ at each spin and the spin current flowing through each bond at resonance for a tetramer with $J_2/J_1 = 0.3$. Only short times are shown in order to facilitate the analysis. As expected, the spin currents flowing through the inter-dimer bonds are much larger than those within each dimer. In addition, a clear correlation is observed between bonds 2–3 and 4–1, whose currents appear to be in antiphase.

Overall, the results obtained up to this point are consistent with the theoretical concepts associated with spin currents. Nevertheless, in order to further reinforce the validity of the calculations, an additional analysis based on the study of the active frequencies in the system dynamics has been carried out. To this end, the state is evolved for a sufficiently long time and the Fourier transform of the instantaneous current $J(t)$ is computed using NumPy routines.

This spectral analysis is relevant because, in a quantum system, the temporal oscillations of any observable, including the spin current, are determined by the interference between the eigenstates of the Hamiltonian. If the initial state can be written as a superposition of eigenstates $|n\rangle$ with energies E_n , the time evolution introduces factors of the form $e^{-i(E_n - E_m)t}$. Therefore, the only frequencies that can appear in $J(t)$ are precisely the energy differences

$$\omega_{mn} = |E_m - E_n|.$$

Consequently, the peaks observed in the FFT spectrum must correspond to transitions between energy levels of the system Hamiltonian.

Comparing the frequencies present in the FFT with the calculated energy *gaps* provides an independent validation of the dynamics: if the spectral peaks coincide with these energy differences, it can be stated that the system is evolving coherently with the proposed model and that the mechanisms responsible for the spin current are correctly identified.

In this case, the frequencies, multiplied by the characteristic factor 2π , are plotted together with the magnitudes of the computed Fourier transform:

Figure 17: Representation of the local expectation value $\langle S^z \rangle$ at each spin and the total spin current in resonance for a tetramer with $J_2/J_1 = 0.3$. In addition, the lower-left panel shows the result obtained from applying Fourier analysis to the global spin current expectation value. The vertical lines correspond to the energy gaps between different states; for example, the red line represents the energy difference between the first triplet state and the ground state, while the purple line corresponds to the gap between the second triplet and the first triplet. As expected, the active frequencies in the system correspond to specific transitions between states and their associated energy differences.

At this point, the only remaining question is whether the original motivation of this project is fulfilled, namely, whether a spin photovoltaic effect can be observed in this Heisenberg model. As discussed above, such an effect occurs if a direct current (DC) appears in the system and if this current exhibits a quadratic dependence on the drive amplitude. This leads to the final problem to be addressed: how to compute this DC current.

The DC current is, in essence, the component of the spin current that remains once all oscillations induced by the external field are removed. In the system under study, the applied field varies periodically in time, and therefore the total current $J(t)$ oscillates following this excitation and its harmonics. However, if a genuine spin photovoltaic effect is present, in addition to these oscillatory components there must be a small fraction

of the current that does not vary in time, namely, a constant current. This is the DC current that we aim to detect. Furthermore, in order to claim the existence of a spin photovoltaic effect, the relationship between the DC current and the drive amplitude must be quadratic, as demonstrated in Refs. [4, 7].

From a conceptual point of view, computing the DC current is straightforward. If the system is allowed to evolve for a sufficiently long time and the temporal average of the current is computed, all oscillatory components cancel out automatically. The only contribution that survives the averaging procedure is precisely the constant one. In practice, we define the DC current as

$$J_{\text{DC}} = \frac{1}{T_{\text{obs}}} \int_0^{T_{\text{obs}}} J(t) dt, \quad (44)$$

where T_{obs} is the total observation time. In the numerical calculation, this integral is simply replaced by the discrete average of all computed values of $J(t)$. If this average is different from zero, we can conclude that the system is capable of transforming a periodic excitation into a net spin current.

Although other approaches were considered, such as extracting the zero-frequency component of the FFT, the final results were very similar. Moreover, the Fourier-based method requires stricter conditions on periodicity and time-window limits, and was therefore discarded. In addition, to improve the reliability of the calculations, the first 40% of the data were omitted when computing the temporal average.

After performing several tests, the spin photovoltaic effect was successfully detected under certain conditions. The first requirement is that the drive amplitude must remain below 90% of the system resonance frequency, i.e., the energy gap to the first triplet. Moreover, the smaller the amplitude b defined in the previous section (Eq. (8)), the longer the system remains in the perturbative regime. The system is said to be in the perturbative regime as long as the DC current response exhibits a quadratic dependence on the drive amplitude, which is precisely the signature of the spin photovoltaic effect. The second condition is that the system must be exposed to the perturbation for short times. Beyond a certain time t' , the tetramer leaves the perturbative regime and the quadratic relationship between J_{DC} and b is lost.

For the numerical calculations, the period of the driving field was taken as the reference time scale. Accordingly, the simulation time is chosen as $t = nT$, where $T = 2\pi/\omega$ is the drive period. With these considerations, the simulations can be performed and the DC current response of the system can be obtained for different values of b .

Figure 18: Representation of the DC current after a time corresponding to $n = 200$ periods in resonance for a tetramer with $J_2/J_1 = 0.3$. The left panel shows the parabolic dependence of the DC current on the drive amplitude for small values of b . The right panel compares the DC current with a quadratic fit plotted on a logarithmic scale, confirming the presence of a photovoltaic effect in the system.

Figure 19: Left: DC current at $n = 200$ periods in resonance for a tetramer with $J_2/J_1 = 0.3$, shown over a larger range of drive amplitudes than in Fig. 18. As can be seen, beyond a certain amplitude the quadratic dependence on b is lost. Right: evolution of the linear fit of the b^2 dependence shown in Fig. 18 as a function of time. Starting from 200 periods, where the fit is clearly linear, the quality of the fit rapidly degrades, until the spin photovoltaic effect can no longer be identified.

With all these results, it can be stated that for this range of times and values of b , the DC current responds quadratically to the applied perturbation, and therefore a spin photovoltaic effect is present in the alternating-exchange Heisenberg model. However, as previously mentioned, this behavior does not hold for arbitrary parameter values. In fact,

if the simulation time is increased, the effect gradually disappears, as illustrated in the following figures.

Finally, it can be verified that this effect appears only when the symmetry is broken by the alternating exchange. If the DC component is computed for a system with $J_1 = J_2$, the spin current vanishes, and consequently any possible quadratic effect disappears.

4 Variational Quantum Eigensolver

In this chapter, the implementation of the VQE to obtain the ground-state energy of the AEHM is discussed. Following the idea illustrated in Fig. 9, a quantum variational scheme is implemented to estimate the ground-state energy of the Heisenberg model with alternating exchange and periodic boundary conditions. As has been shown throughout this work, the Hamiltonian of the system is expressed as in Eq. 1, where J_1 and J_2 are fixed to the values 1 and 0.3 throughout this section, and periodic boundary conditions are considered in order to preserve the translational symmetry of the system. For the computational part, the PennyLane library has been used, a Python-based tool that allows the programming of hybrid quantum algorithms by combining quantum circuits with classical Machine Learning frameworks through automatic differentiation [35].

The chosen reference state corresponds to a valence-bond-type configuration, formed by singlet pairs on contiguous sites, which reflects the natural tendency of the system to form local antiferromagnetic bonds. It can already be assumed as known that the model may be interpreted as a succession of dimers connected to each other through a weaker interaction J_2 , which couples adjacent pairs. In the ground state, each of these dimers is found in the singlet state. The wave function of a singlet is given by

$$|\psi_s\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|01\rangle - |10\rangle), \quad (45)$$

where $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ represent spin-up and spin-down states, respectively. This state can be represented by means of quantum gates as described in [8], specifically:

Figure 20: Quantum circuit that generates the singlet state $(|01\rangle - |10\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$ from the computational basis state $|00\rangle$. The circuit uses a sequence of X , H , $CNOT$, and Z gates to prepare the antisymmetric combination characteristic of the state that represents a dimer in the quantum circuit.

Starting from this basis, the variational ansatz is constructed by successive layers of

parameterized gates applied to neighboring pairs of qubits. Each layer alternates the application of operations on even bonds $(0, 1), (2, 3), \dots$ and odd bonds $(1, 2), (3, 4), \dots$, thus ensuring connectivity and compliance with periodic boundary conditions. These gates implement isotropic unitary transformations that simulate effective evolutions under Heisenberg-type interactions through combinations of Ising rotations (XX, YY, ZZ) , controlled by a single parameter θ per bond. The PennyLane library already includes these circuits, which makes them straightforward to implement. In this case, the form of the circuit that produces a one-layer ansatz for a tetramer is as follows:

Figure 21: Quantum circuit corresponding to the variational ansatz of a tetramer with one layer. Each coupled bond, i.e., each sequence of CNOT, RZ, CNOT, RX gates, is parameterized by a single variational parameter θ_i , so that a complete layer contains N variational parameters in total. The left-hand side prepares singlet-type states from the computational basis state $|00\rangle$, while the rotations $R_X(\theta_i)$ and $R_Z(\theta_i)$ modulate the quantum correlations within each dimer at each iteration. In this way, the layer captures the short-range entanglement physics characteristic of valence-bond-type states. Note that this circuit only serves to calculate expectation values along the Z axis; to calculate X and Y components, additional rotations are required, which will be explained later.

Starting from this initial state, the variational optimization is performed by adjusting the parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ of the ansatz through an energy minimization scheme. To this end, the Adam (Adaptive Moment Estimation) algorithm is employed, a stochastic gradient-descent method that updates each parameter adaptively based on the history of the gradients.

At each iteration of the VQE, the parameterized circuit $|\psi(\boldsymbol{\theta})\rangle$ is evaluated on the different Pauli operators that compose the Hamiltonian, in the case of this project combinations of X , Y , and Z terms. What actually occurs in this process is that the ansatz is

executed repeatedly on the quantum processor, but each execution includes, in addition to the variational gates, a series of additional rotations that allow the final measurement in the computational basis to be interpreted as an effective measurement of the desired observable. The hardware can only measure in the Z basis, so in order to obtain, for example, an expectation value associated with X , the state is previously rotated by means of a Hadamard gate, such that the measurement in the computational basis is equivalent to measuring X . Similarly, to measure a Y operator, appropriate sequences such as $S^\dagger H$ are applied, implementing the required basis change [18]. These rotations are not explicitly specified in the code, since the PennyLane library automatically inserts them whenever the evaluation of an expectation value $\langle P \rangle$ associated with a Pauli operator P is requested.

Once the observable is defined and the corresponding basis transformation is applied, the quantum processor executes the circuit a fixed number of times (“shots”), typically of the order of 10^3 . Each execution ends with a binary outcome 0 or 1 for each measured qubit, corresponding to eigenvalues ± 1 of the Pauli operator effectively evaluated. From the relative frequencies of occurrence of $+1$ and -1 , a statistical estimate of the expectation value of the observable is obtained. In probabilistic terms, if p_+ and p_- represent the estimated probabilities of obtaining $+1$ and -1 , the expectation value is given by $\langle P \rangle \approx p_+ - p_-$.

The intrinsically statistical nature of quantum measurement introduces an uncertainty in the estimation, whose typical error decreases as $1/\sqrt{n_{\text{shots}}}$ due to the central limit theorem [21]. This fluctuation, known as *shot noise*, constitutes one of the main limits to the precision of variational algorithms executed on real hardware.

With all these expectation values, the approximate value of the Hamiltonian energy is reconstructed according to its decomposition in terms of Pauli operators. This is equivalent to performing the calculation

$$E(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \langle \psi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) | H | \psi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \rangle.$$

In the next step, the optimizer computes the gradients of $E(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ with respect to each ansatz parameter and uses them to generate an updated parameter set $\boldsymbol{\theta}'$. Unlike standard gradient descent, Adam does not employ a single fixed learning rate, but instead maintains two moving moments of the gradient: the first (m_n) corresponds to an exponential average of the gradients, while the second (v_n) accumulates information about the squared gradients and controls the magnitude of the update step. To avoid numerical instabilities, the parameter ϵ regularizes the division when v_n is small. In this way, each

ansatz parameter is updated as

$$\theta_{n+1} = \theta_n - \eta \frac{m_n}{\sqrt{v_n} + \epsilon},$$

where η is the effective learning rate.

In the implemented code, this procedure is executed using *qml.AdamOptimizer* from PennyLane. At each iteration, the optimizer calls the function that evaluates the circuit energy, obtains its gradients, and produces a new set of parameters. Periodically, the current variational energy can be stored, allowing the convergence toward the ground state to be studied. The inclusion of the adaptive moments m_n and v_n makes the descent trajectory more stable and efficient, reducing oscillations and avoiding stagnation in flat regions of parameter space. As a result, the VQE scheme is observed to converge consistently toward the energy minimum:

Figure 22: Energy obtained using the VQE algorithm on a simulator for a chain of $N = 12$ sites and two layers, compared with the exact value obtained by diagonalization. Throughout the iterations, the variational energy decreases monotonically and approaches the exact ground-state value, demonstrating the correct optimization of the ansatz parameters and the effectiveness of the Adam optimizer in finding the minimum.

On the other hand, the effect of adding more variational layers to the circuit can be analyzed. To this end, the second part of the circuit shown in Fig. 21 is simply duplicated, resulting in twice as many variational parameters θ . Although this leads to a longer circuit, it yields greater precision and stability as the number of iterations increases. This can be observed by computing the fidelity of the result as $|\langle \psi_{VQE} | \psi_{exact} \rangle|^2$.

Figure 23: Fidelity of the results for obtaining the ground state of a Heisenberg chain with alternating exchange of 12 spins using the VQE algorithm on a classical computer. Although the runs start from different initial values, since these are generated randomly, increasing the number of layers in the initial ansatz leads to greater stability and a better approximation to the ground state.

It is also relevant to ask why it is necessary to resort to quantum computers. In this sense, although the ground-state energy can be calculated exactly through diagonalization of the Hamiltonian, this approach has a computational cost that grows exponentially with the size of the system, as previously discussed. For a chain of N spin-1/2 particles, the dimension of the Hilbert space is 2^N , so the number of elements of the matrix to be diagonalized becomes unmanageable as N increases. This limits the applicability of exact methods to small systems, even when using high-performance computing architectures and advanced parallelization techniques. Quantum computers, on the other hand, offer an alternative with more favorable scaling, since they allow quantum states of exponential dimension to be represented using a linear number of qubits and unitary operations to be implemented through circuits of controlled depth. In this context, hybrid algorithms such as the VQE exploit the ability of quantum devices to manipulate information in high-dimensional spaces without the need to construct or store full matrices in memory.

This is reflected in the fact that the computer used for this work can only calculate systems of up to 14 spins using the diagonalization method, since this would result in a matrix of size $2^{14} \times 2^{14}$. By contrast, a quantum computer would only require 14 qubits to represent the system and perform the energy calculation.

However, given the impossibility of performing the calculations on a real quantum computer, the importance of this quantum algorithm can only be appreciated theoretically, since at the classical level (in a simulator) the scalability problem still remains, albeit

to a lesser extent. In fact, if we use the *eigsh* function from SciPy, which employs the Implicitly Restarted Lanczos method to obtain eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the matrix, it is observed to achieve significantly better performance than the simulator.

Finally, once the implementation of the algorithm and the obtained results have been described, it is necessary to analyze the practical limitations associated with the application of the VQE on real quantum hardware. First, the statistical nature of the measurements introduces intrinsic noise: in order to accurately estimate the expectation values of each term in the Hamiltonian, a large number of *shots* is required, which substantially increases the total computation time.

Moreover, the energy estimation procedure also has a considerable experimental cost. In a one-dimensional Heisenberg model, each bond contributes three Pauli terms (XX, YY, ZZ), so that for a chain of L sites a total of $3(L - 1)$ different circuits must be evaluated at each VQE iteration. Each of these circuits must be executed a large number of times to obtain a statistically reliable estimate of the corresponding expectation value. The typical uncertainty associated with a quantum measurement is of order $1/\sqrt{N_{\text{shots}}}$, so achieving reasonable resolution generally requires more than $N_{\text{shots}} \sim 10^3$ repetitions of the same circuit.

Since the variational process requires several tens of iterations to converge (typically more than 30), the total number of hardware executions grows rapidly according to

$$N_{\text{total}} \approx N_{\text{iter}} N_{\text{shots}} 3(L - 1),$$

which, for example, for $N_{\text{iter}} = 30$, $N_{\text{shots}} = 1000$, and a four-site chain ($L = 4$), implies approximately 2.7×10^5 circuit executions. This accumulation of hardware calls, together with the intrinsic noise of the device, constitutes one of the main practical limitations in the implementation of variational algorithms. To this experimental burden one must add the phenomenon of *barren plateaus*, regions of parameter space in which the gradient of the energy functional becomes so small that it is essentially indistinguishable from zero within the statistical error introduced by the *shots*. In these regimes, the variance of the gradient decreases exponentially with the number of qubits, so that even if the quantum state is executed correctly, the useful signal is overwhelmed by statistical measurement noise. As a consequence, the optimizer receives practically no information about the direction in which the parameters should be updated, causing the iterative process to stall or to explore parameter space erratically. This behavior is particularly pronounced in deep or overly expressive ansatzes, where concentration of measure leads to nearly uniform gradient distributions. In practice, the appearance of *barren plateaus* severely

limits the scalability of variational methods and constitutes one of the main bottlenecks of current hybrid quantum–classical algorithms.

Furthermore, the decomposition of the Hamiltonian into Pauli operators can generate a very large number of terms to be measured, further increasing the total cost. All these factors imply that, despite its theoretical potential and favorable scaling, the practical implementation of the VQE on real systems is still limited by noise, statistics, and the resources required to obtain precise results.

5 Conclusions

En general, it can be said that the results of the project have been very satisfactory, since all the objectives proposed for it have been achieved. Despite being two objectives with considerable uncertainty, given that there were not many published references on the outcomes of this work, the results have been very conclusive, and each step could be consistently verified.

On one hand, it is worth highlighting that the spin photovoltaic effect has been demonstrated in a Heisenberg ring. It is true that this effect only applies for small values of time and perturbation amplitude, but it could serve as a basis for further research and opens a window of possibilities for continued investigation within the framework of condensed matter physics.

On the other hand, the project has successfully understood and implemented the *Variational Quantum Eigensolver* (VQE) to obtain the ground state of the given Hamiltonian. This has represented an interesting journey through quantum computing and the application of current quantum algorithms and their possibilities. It should be noted that we are still at a very early stage of this technology, and it is difficult to predict its potential in the coming decades. However, all indications suggest that, if development continues in this direction, significant advances could occur both in various fields of science and in computing in general. Nevertheless, to put it into context, if one wanted to apply it to real-world problems, the number of terms in a quantum chemistry Hamiltonian (atoms, molecules, solids) scales as N^4 , where N is the number of orbitals, meaning that the number of qubits required would also be very large to tackle such a problem.

As for future projects, the spin photovoltaic effect found in this master's thesis could be studied systematically, analyzing the impact of the dimerization value $\frac{J_1-J_2}{J_1+J_2}$ or the frequency of the drive. In addition, other types of perturbations could be considered, such as the Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya (DM) interaction [41]. Moreover, the implementation of VQE on real quantum computers, for example on the IBM platform, could be explored with a budget to study.

Finally, at a personal level, this project has been very interesting. Theoretically, it has helped consolidate knowledge of spin models, which was relatively new in my academic trajectory. Practically, it required learning to use new libraries, which strengthened my programming foundation. It is also worth mentioning that, since this project deals with a relatively new topic, it has reinforced my analytical skills and intuition, as they were frequently necessary.

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Appendix I

In this appendix is the code used to obtain the results with the VQE.

```
1 # vqe_alternating_heisenberg_pbc.py
2 # Requisitos: pennylane, numpy
3 # pip install pennylane
4
5 import pennylane as qml
6 import numpy as np
7 import numpy.linalg as la
8 from quspin.operators import hamiltonian
9 from quspin.basis import spin_basis_1d
10 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
11
12 # -----
13 # Parametros del problema
14 # -----
15 J1 = 1.0
16 J2 = 0.3
17 PBC = True          # condiciones periodicas: True -> anade
18                     termino (N-1,0)
19 seed = 42
20 np.random.seed(seed)
21 # -----
22 # Construccion del Hamiltoniano (matriz) para exact
23 # diagonalization
24 # -----
25 def H_hac_b(L, J1, J2, start_with_J1 = True, pbc=True):
26     bonds = []
27     bonds_xy = []
28
29     for i in range(L-1):
30         useJ = J1 if ((i % 2 == 0) == start_with_J1) else J2
31         bonds.append([useJ/1.0, i, i+1])
32         bonds_xy.append([useJ/2.0, i, i+1])
```

```

33     if pbc and L > 1:
34         i = L-1
35         useJ = J1 if ((i % 2 == 0) == start_with_J1) else J2
36         bonds.append([useJ/1.0, L-1, 0])
37         bonds_xy.append([useJ/2.0, L-1, 0])
38     static_H0 = [{"+-", bonds_xy}, {"-+", bonds_xy}, ["zz", bonds]]
39     dynamic_empty = []
40
41     basis = spin_basis_1d(L, pauli=0)
42     H0 = hamiltonian(static_H0, dynamic_empty, basis=basis, dtype=
43         np.complex128,
44         check_pcon=False, check_herm=False, check_symm
45             =False)
46     return H0, basis, static_H0
47
48 # -----
49 # Construcción del Hamiltoniano para PennyLane
50 # -----
51 def build_pennyLane_hamiltonian(N, J1, J2, pbc=True):
52     """Devuelve (coeffs, observables) para qml.Hamiltonian"""
53     coeffs = []
54     obs = []
55     for i in range(N):
56         j = (i+1) % N
57         if (not pbc) and (i == N-1):
58             break
59         J = J1 if (i % 2 == 0) else J2
60         # terminos X_i X_j, Y_i Y_j, Z_i Z_j con factor 1/4 por la
61         # conversión de matrices de Pauli a espin
62         coeffs += [J/4.0, J/4.0, J/4.0]
63         obs += [qml.PauliX(i) @ qml.PauliX(j),
64             qml.PauliY(i) @ qml.PauliY(j),
65             qml.PauliZ(i) @ qml.PauliZ(j)]
66     H = qml.Hamiltonian(coeffs, obs)
67     return H
68
69 # -----

```

```

67 # Estado de referencia: valence-bond (pares singlete en (0,1)
    ,(2,3),...)
68 # -----
69 def valence_bond_preparation(N):
70     """Prepara singletes aproximados en pares (0,1),(2,3),..."""
71     # singlete = (|01> - |10>)/sqrt(2)
72     Nloc = N
73     for k in range(0, Nloc, 2):
74         qml.PauliX(wires=k+1)
75         qml.Hadamard(wires=k)
76         qml.CNOT(wires=[k, k+1])
77         qml.PauliZ(wires=k)
78
79 # -----
80 # Puerta parametrizada tipo eSWAP
81 # -----
82 def eSWAP_like(a, b, theta):
83     """
84     Aplica una puerta del tipo  $\exp(-i * \theta * (XX + YY + ZZ)/2)$ 
        aproximada
85     usando rotaciones Ising. Un unico parametro theta aqui.
86     """
87     qml.IsingXX(theta, wires=[a, b])
88     qml.IsingYY(theta, wires=[a, b])
89     qml.IsingZZ(theta, wires=[a, b])
90
91 # -----
92 # Circuito ansatz (capas alternadas: even-odd then odd-even)
93 # -----
94 def make_ansatz(params, N, nlayers):
95     """
96     params: arreglo (nlayers, n_pair_per_layer)
97     Primero se aplican enlaces pares, luego impares
98     """
99     valence_bond_preparation(N)
100    for L in range(nlayers):
101        p_idx = 0
102        # even bonds

```

```

103     for i in range(0, N, 2):
104         j = (i+1) % N
105         eSWAP_like(i, j, params[L, p_idx])
106         p_idx += 1
107     # odd bonds
108     for i in range(1, N, 2):
109         j = (i+1) % N
110         eSWAP_like(i, j, params[L, p_idx])
111         p_idx += 1
112
113 def VQE(N, J1, J2, nlayers, niter):
114     """
115     VQE para obtener el estado fundamental del modelo de Heisenberg
116     .
117     """
118     Eiter = np.array([])
119     Psiiter = np.array([])
120     dev = qml.device("default.qubit", wires=N)
121     nparams_per_layer = N
122     H_pennylane = build_pennylane_hamiltonian(N, J1, J2, pbc=PBC)
123
124     @qml.qnode(dev)
125     def circuit_expectation(params):
126         make_ansatz(params, N, nlayers)
127         return qml.expval(H_pennylane)
128
129     @qml.qnode(dev)
130     def circuit_state(params):
131         make_ansatz(params, N, nlayers)
132         return qml.state()
133
134     # Diagonalizacion exacta
135     Hmat, _, _ = H_hac_b(N, J1, J2, pbc=PBC)
136     eigvals, eigvecs = Hmat.eigh()
137     E_exact = np.real(eigvals[0])
138     psi_exact = eigvecs[:, 0]
139
140     # -----

```

```

140     # Optimizacion VQE
141     # -----
142     params = 0.1 * np.random.randn(nlayers, nparams_per_layer,
143                                   requires_grad=True)
143     opt = qml.AdamOptimizer(stepsize=0.01)
144     max_iters = niter
145
146     print("Iniciando VQE...")
147     for it in range(1, max_iters + 1):
148         params = opt.step(circuit_expectation, params)
149         if (it % 2 == 0) or (it == 1):
150             E = circuit_expectation(params)
151             Eiter = np.append(Eiter, E)
152
153             psi_vqe = np.asarray(circuit_state(params))
154             overlap = np.vdot(psi_exact, psi_vqe)
155             Psiiter = np.append(Psiiter, np.abs(overlap)**2)
156
157     E_vqe = float(circuit_expectation(params))
158
159     psi_vqe = np.asarray(circuit_state(params))
160     overlap = np.vdot(psi_exact, psi_vqe)
161     fidelity = np.abs(overlap)**2
162
163     return E_vqe, Eiter, fidelity, E_exact, Psiiter
164
165 # Numero de iteraciones
166 iter = 30
167
168 # Calculo con los valores
169 evqe2, td2, tvqe2, Eiter2, f2, ed2, fiter2 = VQE(12, J1, J2, 1,
170         iter)

```

Appendix II

In this appendix is the code used to obtain the results with the QuSpin.

```

1 # dimer_resonance_scan.py
2 from __future__ import print_function, division
3 import numpy as np
4 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
5 import matplotlib as mpl
6 from quspin.operators import hamiltonian
7 from quspin.basis import spin_basis_1d
8
9 #Hamiltoniano estatico
10
11 def H_hac_b(L, J1, J2, h_z=1e-4, start_with_J1 = True, pbc=True):
12     bonds = []
13     bonds_xy = []
14
15     for i in range(L-1):
16         useJ = J1 if ((i % 2 == 0) == start_with_J1) else J2
17         bonds.append([useJ/1.0, i, i+1])
18         bonds_xy.append([useJ/2.0, i, i+1])
19
20     if pbc and L > 1:
21         i = L-1
22         useJ = J1 if ((i % 2 == 0) == start_with_J1) else J2
23         bonds.append([useJ/1.0, L-1, 0])
24         bonds_xy.append([useJ/2.0, L-1, 0])
25     field_term = [{"z", [[h_z, i] for i in range(L)]]]
26     static_H0 = [{"+-", bonds_xy}, {"-+", bonds_xy}, {"zz", bonds}]
27     + field_term
28     dynamic_empty = []
29
30     basis = spin_basis_1d(L, pauli=0)
31     H0 = hamiltonian(static_H0, dynamic_empty, basis=basis, dtype=
        np.complex128,
        check_pcon=False, check_herm=False, check_symm=
        False)

```

```

32     return H0, basis, static_H0
33
34 #Operadores utiles
35
36 def build_spin_current_operator(basis, L, J1, J2, start_with_J1=
    True, pbc=True):
37
38     curr_plus_minus = [] # lista para terminos  $S^+_{l} S^-_{l+1}$ 
39     curr_minus_plus = [] # lista para terminos  $S^-_{l} S^+_{l+1}$ 
40
41     for i in range(L - 1):
42         useJ = J1 if ((i % 2 == 0) == start_with_J1) else J2
43         curr_plus_minus.append([1j * useJ / 2, i, i + 1])
44         curr_minus_plus.append([-1j * useJ / 2, i, i + 1])
45
46     # Periodic Boundary Conditions (si se desea)
47     if pbc and L > 1:
48         i = L - 1
49         j = 0
50         useJ = J1 if ((i % 2 == 0) == start_with_J1) else J2
51         curr_plus_minus.append([1j * useJ / 2, i, j])
52         curr_minus_plus.append([-1j * useJ / 2, i, j])
53
54     static_J = [{"+-", curr_plus_minus}, {"-+", curr_minus_plus}]
55
56     J_op = hamiltonian(
57         static_J, [], basis=basis, dtype=np.complex128,
58         check_pcon=False, check_herm=False, check_symm=False
59     )
60
61     return J_op
62
63 def Sz_operator_site(basis, site):
64     static = [{"z", [[1.0, site]]}]
65     dynamic = []
66     Sz = hamiltonian(static, dynamic, basis=basis, dtype=np.float64
    ,

```

```

67         check_pcon=False, check_herm=False, check_symm
           =False)
68
69     return Sz
70
71 def build_local_spin_currents_local(basis, L, J1, J2, start_with_J1
   =True, pbc=True):
72     """
73     Devuelve una lista de operadores de corriente de espín  $J_i$ ,
74     uno por cada enlace  $(i, i+1)$ .
75     """
76     J_ops = []
77     n_links = L if pbc else L - 1
78
79     for i in range(n_links):
80         j = (i + 1) % L
81         useJ = J1 if ((i % 2 == 0) == start_with_J1) else J2
82
83         # Definición local de corriente entre sitios  $i$  y  $j$ 
84         curr_plus_minus = [[1j * useJ / 2, i, j]]
85         curr_minus_plus = [[-1j * useJ / 2, i, j]]
86         static_J = [{"+-", curr_plus_minus}, {"-+", curr_minus_plus
           }]
87
88         J_local = hamiltonian(
89             static_J, [],
90             basis=basis,
91             dtype=np.complex128,
92             check_pcon=False,
93             check_herm=False,
94             check_symm=False
95         )
96         J_ops.append(J_local)
97
98     return J_ops
99
100 def compute_DC_current(J_expect, times, t_skip=0.2, use_fft=False,
   window=None):

```

```
101     dt = times[1] - times[0]
102     N = len(times)
103
104     if 0.0 <= t_skip < 1.0:
105         t0 = times[int(N * t_skip)]
106     else:
107         t0 = t_skip
108     idx0 = np.searchsorted(times, t0)
109
110     tail = J_expect[idx0:]
111     if len(tail) == 0:
112         return 0.0, None, None, None
113
114     J_mean = np.mean(tail).real
115
116     DC_from_fft = None
117     fourier = None
118     freqs = None
119     if use_fft:
120         x = tail - np.mean(tail)
121         if window == 'hann':
122             w = np.hanning(len(x))
123             xw = x * w
124         else:
125             xw = x
126
127         fourier = np.fft.fft(xw)
128         freqs = np.fft.fftfreq(len(xw), d=dt)
129         DC_from_fft = J_mean
130
131     return J_mean, DC_from_fft, fourier, freqs
132
133 # Hamiltoniano dinamico
134
135 def V_t(t, w, b):
136     return b * np.cos(w * t)
137
```

```

138 # helper: crear H(t) para una omega dada (necesitamos recrear para
      cada omega)
139 def make_Ht(omega_val, b_val, J1, J2, h_z=1e-4):
140     _, basis, static_H = H_hac_b(L, J1, J2, h_z, pbc=PBC)
141     dynamic_V = [{"x", [[1.0, 0]], V_t, (omega_val, b_val)}]
142     Ht = hamiltonian(static_H, dynamic_V, basis=basis, dtype=np.
      complex128,
143                     check_pcon=False, check_herm=False, check_symm
      =False)
144     return Ht
145
146 #Dimero
147
148 def analyze_dimer(omega_val, b_val, times):
149     Ht = make_Ht(omega_val, b_val)
150     evals, evecs = H0.eigh()
151     E0, E1, E2, E3 = evals
152     psi0, psi1, psi2, psi3 = evecs.T
153
154     psi_t_all = Ht.evolve(psi0, 0.0, times, iterate=True, rtol=1e
      -9, atol=1e-12)
155
156     P01 = np.zeros(len(times), dtype=float)
157     P02 = np.zeros(len(times), dtype=float)
158     P03 = np.zeros(len(times), dtype=float)
159     P00 = np.zeros(len(times), dtype=float)
160     E_t = np.zeros(len(times), dtype=float)
161
162     for i, psi in enumerate(psi_t_all):
163         psi = psi / np.linalg.norm(psi)
164         Vval = b_val * np.cos(omega_val * times[i])
165         E_t[i] = np.vdot(psi, H0.dot(psi)).real + Vval * np.vdot(
      psi, Sx.dot(psi)).real
166         P01[i] = np.abs(np.vdot(psi, psi1))**2
167         P00[i] = np.abs(np.vdot(psi, psi0))**2
168         P02[i] = np.abs(np.vdot(psi, psi2))**2
169         P03[i] = np.abs(np.vdot(psi, psi3))**2
170

```

```

171     E_state0 = E0 * P00
172     E_state1 = E1 * P01
173     E_state2 = E2 * P02
174     E_state3 = E3 * P03
175
176     E_avg = E_state0 + E_state1 + E_state2 + E_state3
177
178     # Retorna todo
179     return P00, P01, P02, P03, E_t, E_state0, E_state1, E_state2,
180           E_state3, E_avg
181
182     P00, P01, P02, P03, E_t, E_state0, E_state1, E_state2, E_state3,
183     E_avg = analyze_dimer(1, 1, times)
184
185     #Tetramero
186
187     def analyze_tetramer(omega_val, b_val, times, J1=1.0, J2=0.3, pbc=
188         True, hz=1e-4):
189
190         H0, basis, stat = H_hac_b(L, J1, J2, pbc=pbc, h_z=hz)
191         Ht = make_Ht(omega_val, b_val, J1, J2, h_z=hz)
192         evals, evecs = H0.eigh()
193         psi0 = evecs[:, 0]
194         psi_t_all = Ht.evolve(psi0, 0.0, times, iterate=True, rtol=1e
195             -9, atol=1e-12)
196
197         n_states = len(evals)
198         n_times = len(times)
199
200         # --- Matriz de probabilidades ---
201         P_matrix = np.zeros((n_states, n_times), dtype=float)
202         E_t = np.zeros(n_times, dtype=float)
203
204         Sz_ops = [Sz_operator_site(basis, i) for i in range(L)]
205         Sz_expect = np.zeros((L, n_times), dtype=np.complex128)
206
207         J_op = build_spin_current_operator(basis, L, J1, J2, pbc=pbc)
208         J_expect = np.zeros(len(times), dtype=np.complex128)

```

```

205     J_ops = build_local_spin_currents_local(basis, L, J1, J2, pbc=
        pbc)
206     J_local_expect = np.zeros((len(J_ops), len(times)), dtype=np.
        complex128)
207     M = J_op.todense()
208     Sx = hamiltonian([[ "x", [[1.0, 0]]]], [], basis=basis, dtype=np.
        .complex128, check_pcon=False, check_herm=False, check_symm=
        False)
209
210     for i, psi in enumerate(psi_t_all):
211         psi = psi / np.linalg.norm(psi)
212         Vval = b_val * np.cos(omega_val * times[i])
213
214         # Energia instantanea
215         E_t[i] = np.vdot(psi, H0.dot(psi)).real + Vval * np.vdot(
            psi, Sx.dot(psi)).real
216
217         # Probabilidades de proyeccion sobre cada autovector de H0
218         Pi = np.abs(np.dot(np.conjugate(evecs.T), psi))**2
219         P_matrix[:, i] = Pi
220
221         for j in range(L):
222             Sz_expect[j, i] = np.vdot(psi, Sz_ops[j].dot(psi)).real
223         for link, Jop in enumerate(J_ops):
224             J_local_expect[link, i] = np.vdot(psi, Jop.dot(psi)).
                real
225
226         J_expect[i] = np.vdot(psi, J_op.dot(psi)).real
227
228     #Agrupamientos para el tetramero
229     idx_singlet_1 = [0]
230     idx_triplet_1 = [1, 2, 3]
231     idx_triplet_2 = [4, 5, 6]
232     idx_singlet_2 = [7]
233     idx_triplet_3 = [8, 9, 10]
234     idx_quintet   = [11, 12, 13, 14, 15]
235
236     # --- Probabilidades agrupadas ---

```

```

237     P_singlet1 = np.sum(P_matrix[idx_singlet_1], axis=0)
238     P_triplet1 = np.sum(P_matrix[idx_triplet_1], axis=0)
239     P_triplet2 = np.sum(P_matrix[idx_triplet_2], axis=0)
240     P_singlet2 = np.sum(P_matrix[idx_singlet_2], axis=0)
241     P_triplet3 = np.sum(P_matrix[idx_triplet_3], axis=0)
242     P_quintet  = np.sum(P_matrix[idx_quintet],   axis=0)
243
244     return P_singlet1, P_triplet1, P_triplet2, P_singlet2,
           P_triplet3, P_quintet, E_t, evals, Sz_expect.real, J_expect,
           P_matrix[1,:], P_matrix[2,:], P_matrix[3,:], J_local_expect
245
246     L = 4
247     J1 = 1.0
248     J2 = 0.3
249     PBC = True
250
251     H0, base , _ = H_hac_b(L, J1, J2, pbc=PBC, h_z=1e-4)
252     # diagonaliza H0 completamente para obtener niveles
253     evals, evecs = H0.eigh()
254     gap =evals[1]-evals[0]
255
256     b=0.002
257     #tmax = 1414*2
258     omega = gap
259     T = 2*np.pi/omega
260     n_periods = 1000 # reducimos un poco para tiempo de ejecucion
261     tmax = n_periods * T
262     nsteps = int(tmax/0.25)
263     times = np.linspace(0.0, tmax, nsteps)
264
265     P_singlet1, P_triplet1, P_triplet2, P_singlet2, P_triplet3,
           P_quintet, E_t, energias, Sz_expect, Jexp, P_t1_1, P_t1_2,
           P_t1_3, J_local = analyze_tetramer(gap, b, times, J1=J1, J2=J2,
           pbc=PBC, hz=1e-4)
266
267     jmed, dc, fourier, fr = compute_DC_current(Jexp, times)

```